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Facial Expressions and Facial Micro Expressions Recognition Using RGB-D Images and Videos

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Abstract:

The human face states the inner emotions, thoughts, and physical disorders. These emotions are expressed on the face via facial muscles. Research indicates that facial expressions are the best way to express emotions. Human facial expressions and micro-expressions could be studied in the images and digital video frames. The estimated time through which a facial expression occurs is between 0.5 to 4 seconds and a micro expression between 0.1-0.5. Also, in some references, this value is stated as 1.3, 1.15, and 1.25 seconds. Obviously, for the purpose of recording micro-expressions, obtaining video frames between 30 and 200 fps is essential. Before depth sensors emerged, facial expression recognition (FER) was done only by color images. However, after depth sensors emerged, and due to more data (depth dimension), the recognition rate in FER increased significantly. This was tangible for a decade in this field. Facial expression recognition has applications in human-computer (robot) interaction, 2D and 3D animation, psychology, non-verbal communication or body language, emotion recognition, security issues such as lie detection, etc. Features which are used in this study are Histogram of Oriented Gradient (HOG), Gabor Filter, Speeded Up Robust Features (SURF), Local Phase Quantization (LPQ), Local Binary Pattern (LBP), and Haar Feature. Due to the shortage of RGB-D FER database, and also due to available databases weaknesses, a database including 40 individuals or subjects in a variety of ages and genders with the Kinect V.2 sensor is gathered, which to the extent acceptable has resolved the available databases with similar features weaknesses. On the other hand, it can be said that this is the first depth database for facial micro expression recognition (FMER). This database is named the Iranian Kinect Face Database (IKFDB). Considering that Kinect's acquired data is divided into color and depth parts, a hybrid feature extraction method for depth data based on pixel distance alterations with a depth sensor is considered. Sections under the titles of age estimation and gender recognition are considered, too. Also, a face detection and extraction algorithm for Depth images is presented. These methods are evaluated and compared with the benchmark databases and the proposed database. Databases used for evaluation are Eurecom Kinect Face DB, VAP RGBD Face DB, VAP RGBD-T Face, JAFFE, IKFDB, Face Grabber DB, Curtin Face, FEEDB, and CASME, which are prepared in two kinds (image and video frames) by different RGB (color), Depth and Thermal sensors. Finally, selected features in the shape of the feature vectors, and for the learning process, are sent to Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Multi-Layer Neural Network (MLNN) classifiers. The results are really satisfactory, and they indicate improvement in classification accuracy in some databases and methods. Also, some of these actions are performed on some of these databases for the first time.

Key Words: Facial Expressions Recognition (FER), Facial Micro Expressions Recognition (FMER), Kinect Depth Sensor, Histogram of Oriented Gradient (HOG), Gabor Filter, Speeded Up Robust Features (SURF), Local Phase Quantization (LPQ), Local Binary Pattern (LBP), Haar Feature, Iranian Kinect Face Data Base (IKFDB), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Multi-Layer Neural Network (MLNN)

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Chapter 1 Introduction

1-1 Preface

Object detection is one of the most important branches of image processing, with human detection, face detection, and facial expression recognition being among the objects of interest for researchers. Over the past decade, we have witnessed the rapid expansion of cameras and their use in various aspects of human life. This expansion has led to significant attention being given to the science of image processing.

Facial expression recognition is one of the challenging areas in computer vision and occurs after the stages of human detection and face detection. Micro-expression recognition, which has recently gained attention, requires even more precise computations. Facial expression and micro-expression recognition can be explained with an example. Suppose we want to count the number of apples on trees, distinguish between green, yellow, and red apples, and finally, separate worm-infested apples from healthy ones. Additionally, we want to identify the type of infestation. If we compare this process to facial recognition, detecting and counting faces is equivalent to detecting and counting apples. Differentiating apples by color corresponds to distinguishing between different individuals, and finally, separating healthy apples from worm-infested ones and identifying the type of infestation is analogous to recognizing facial expressions. Therefore, this process requires highly precise and extensive computations.

A system that can detect humans and faces and subsequently recognize facial expressions is called a facial expression recognition system. There are various methods for face detection, one of which is the Viola and Jones window-based method [1]. Additionally, other methods, such as shape-based approaches like ellipse fitting [2], also exist. Figure 1–1 illustrates examples of face detection.

Figure 1–1 Examples of face detection

In facial expression detection, which stems from human internal emotions, certain points must be considered. First, there is a distinction between face detection and recognition that should not be confused. When one can distinguish a face object from other objects in an image, this process is called face detection. The stage of face recognition and expression detection occurs after detection and determines whose face has been detected and what expression it shows. Therefore, one cannot use the term "expression detection." Figure 1–2 illustrates this concept.

Figure 1–2 Face recognition and expression detection

1-2 Research Objectives

This research aims to achieve automatic recognition of facial expressions and micro-expressions (main topic) as well as age and gender recognition (secondary topic) using image processing techniques. The intended techniques are applied to texture-depth images. Based on observations, this study is the first to focus

on automatic micro-expression recognition. The research seeks to improve the accuracy of facial expression and micro-expression recognition by selecting appropriate features for texture and depth data.

1-3 Research Necessity

As previously mentioned, the field of machine vision and its subset, image processing, are continuously expanding and have extended beyond academic research into various aspects of everyday life. It is no exaggeration to state that without image processing, the modern world would face significant challenges. This field has profoundly influenced daily life, with applications ranging from vehicle speed monitoring and social media networks to security surveillance in banks and retail stores, military industries, psychology and medical sciences, agriculture, and the video game industry, among others. However, certain applications of this discipline hold particular significance, especially when the subject under analysis is the human body—more specifically, the human face. When discussing facial recognition and expression analysis, concepts such as identity verification, security, and the detection of human emotions naturally come to mind. A more in-depth examination reveals that if the image data also contains depth information, additional applications such as 3D facial modeling for animation, age and gender recognition, medical diagnostics, and agricultural research can be considered. But what exactly is depth data? With the advent of depth sensors such as Kinect, Asus Xtion, Minolta, and Inspeck Mega Capturor, the accuracy and level of detail in data acquisition have significantly improved. Depth data is typically represented as grayscale or, in some cases, black-and-white 2D images, where pixel values correspond to the distance between the sensor and the target object. **Error! Reference source not found.** presents the characteristics of some of these depth sensors.

Table 1-1 Characteristics of some depth sensor

Sensor	Type	Resolution (mm)	Working Distance (m)	Price (\$)
Minolta Sensors (Minolta, 2006)	3D Laser Scanning	0.041-0.22	~ 2.5	25000
3dMDface (3dMD, nd)	Vision Cameras	<0.2	—	10k - 20k
CyberWare 3030RGB/PS (Cyberware, nd)	Low-Intensity Laser Light Source	0.08 - 0.3	0.35	~ 72000
Inspeck Mega Capturer II (Savran et al., 2008)	Structured-Light	0.7	1.1	Not Available
Kinect v1 (Microsoft, 2010)	IR laser Emitter	~ 1.5 - 0.5	0.5 - 4.5	Not Available
Kinect v2 (Microsoft, 2014)	Time-of-Flight	-	~ 0.5 - 8	149.99
SoftKinetic DS325 (SofKinetic, 2007)	Diffused Laser	1.4 at 1 m distance	~ 0.15 - 1	259
Structure (Structure, 2013)	IR Structured Light	0.5 - 30	3.5	379
PrimeSense Carmine (I3DU, nd)	IR Laser Emitter	0.1 - 1.2	3.5	Not Available
ASUS Xtion Pro Live (Asus, 2011)	IR Laser Emitter	-	0.8 - 3.5	169.99
Intel RealSense (Intel, 2015a)	Structured Light	<1	~ 0.2 - >10	99 - 399

These images, which can also be used to extract 3D models of objects, utilize various data acquisition technologies. However, the majority of these technologies rely on infrared rays for data capture. For example, the Kinect sensor, currently available in its second version, determines the distance of a given point from an object by emitting infrared rays from the sensor to the target and measuring their reflection. The specifications of Kinect versions 1 and 2 are presented in Figure 1–3.

	Kinect v1		Kinect v2	
	Resolution [Pixel × Pixel]	Frame Rate [Hz]	Resolution [Pixel × Pixel]	Frame Rate [Hz]
color	640 × 480	30	1920 × 1080	30
depth	640 × 480	30	512 × 424	30
infrared	640 × 480	30	512 × 424	30

Kinect V1 vs Kinect V2

Feature	Kinect for Windows 1	Kinect for Windows 2
Color Camera	640 x 480 @ 30 fps	1920 x 1080 @ 30 fps
Depth Camera	320 x 240	512 x 424
Max Depth Distance	~4.5 M	~4.5 M
Min Depth Distance	40 cm in near mode	50 cm
Horizontal Field of View	57 degrees	70 degrees
Vertical Field of View	43 degrees	60 degrees
Tilt Motor	yes	no
Skeleton Joints Defined	20 joints	25 joints
Full Skeletons Tracked	2	6
USB Standard	2.0	3.0
Supported OS	Win 7, Win 8	Win 8-8.1 (WSA)
Price	\$299	TBD

Figure 1–3 Comparison of the features of Kinect sensors, versions 1 and 2 [6] [7]

In this figure, the two versions of the depth sensors are compared in terms of both appearance and hardware specifications. In version 1 of this product, a rotating motor was present, whereas in version 2, this motor was removed. However, in terms of quality and performance, version 2 demonstrates significantly improved capabilities.

The higher the image resolution or sensor capability, the more precise the feature extraction will be. When discussing facial feature extraction, we are essentially analyzing the positioning and structure of facial muscles. If we rely solely on RGB images for recognition, we are limited to the red, green, and blue (RGB) channels. However, by incorporating a fourth dimension—depth—we gain access to additional characteristics such as the indentation of facial lines and muscles, as well as the length and width of facial elements. Naturally, integrating these depth-based attributes with features extracted from color images enhances recognition accuracy. Figure 1–4 illustrates an example of a color image compared to a depth image of a face.

Figure 1–4 Color image (left) and depth image (right) [6]

The infrared beams emitted by the Kinect transmitter (Emitter) collectively form texture and depth data, amount to approximately 300,000 points per frame. Figure 1–6 illustrates the method of calculating the distance of an object from the Kinect sensor based on the triangulation angle. Additionally, Figure 1–5 presents the structure of texture and depth images. Texture images typically contain values ranging between 0 and 256 in each channel, whereas depth images exhibit varying pixel values depending on the type of sensor used. Due to their structural nature, depth images generally have fewer abrupt pixel variations (edges). These two-dimensional depth images can be readily transformed into three-dimensional representations for a wide range of applications.

Figure 1–5 The structure of texture and depth images

Figure 1-6 The method of calculating the distance between an object and the Kinect sensor

For approximately a decade, the use of depth data in various fields of image processing has been a subject of research, analysis, and development. In 2011,

one of the world's leading technology companies, Microsoft, introduced the first version of the Kinect sensor, followed by its second version in 2014, designed for recreational use with the Xbox console as well as for developers. Due to its affordability and relatively high performance, the Kinect sensor gained significant attention from developers, including video game creators, programmers from various disciplines, and technology enthusiasts, eventually becoming a widely used device in academic research. Given the accessibility of this technology and the importance of facial recognition and expression analysis in various domains, further advancements and developments in this field are of great significance. However, many potential applications of this technology remain unexplored. Additionally, research on age and gender recognition using depth data is still limited and underdeveloped. To utilize this technology effectively, there is a pressing need for larger and more accurate databases. Unfortunately, due to the novelty of depth-based technology, not only are the available facial recognition and expression databases that leverage depth data scarce, but they also suffer from various issues, including inadequate lighting, improper camera positioning for each subject, lack of a consistent background, weak or erroneous facial expressions, and—most critically—the failure to account for the distance between the subject and the sensor, which is crucial for depth data accuracy. To address these challenges, the proposed database in this study has been designed to overcome these limitations. Notably, no database for micro-expression recognition has previously been developed for depth data. This research presents, for the first time, a dataset specifically designed for micro-expression recognition using depth information.

1-4 Challenges

The detection of humans and faces, and beyond that, the recognition of facial identities and expressions, can be a challenging task due to varying environmental conditions. Factors such as changes in lighting, the presence of multiple objects resembling human figures and faces in an image, different angles of facial orientation, diverse ethnic facial expressions, similar facial expressions, subtle expressions, and the presence of facial accessories such as

beards and glasses can all significantly impact the accuracy of the final recognition outcome.

1-5 Applications

It is beneficial to first highlight the applications of depth sensors across various scientific fields. These applications include, but are not limited to, human detection, gesture recognition, action recognition, tumor recognition in medical sciences, weight estimation of agricultural and livestock products, robotics, animation and video game industries, assistive technologies for individuals with autism, and retail applications such as virtual eyeglass fitting in optical stores. These are just a few examples of the capabilities offered by this technology.

Facial detection and expression recognition also have a wide range of applications, among which some of the most significant include identity verification, age and gender recognition, emotion detection, 3D facial modeling, security cameras, recognition in complete darkness using depth-only sensors, facial psychology, and human-computer interaction. In robotics, for instance, depth-based facial recognition plays a crucial role in enabling robots to imitate and learn from human actions, non-verbal communication, and body language.

1-6 General Framework for Gender, Face and Expression Detection

The key components of facial and expression recognition include feature extraction, describing extracted features using descriptors in vector form for effective learning, feature selection, pre and post processing steps, training, and classification. If the input data contains a human object, direct facial detection can be performed, or the process can start with pre-processing steps to remove non-human objects before proceeding to face detection. In human and face detection using window-based methods, candidate windows are identified at each stage, and non-human or non-face objects are filtered out. The final steps involve gender classification, face recognition, and expression detection. The same methods can be applied to all these tasks. Gender classification determines whether the individual is male or female. Face recognition identifies the individual's identity, while expression recognition determines the person's

emotional state. A neutral expression, lacking any emotional cues, is also considered one of the classified expressions.

After converting the extracted features into a feature vector, gender classification assigns individuals to two categories: male and female. Face recognition categorizes individuals based on their identity, while expression recognition classifies facial expressions into seven categories: neutral, happy, sad, angry, surprised, disgusted, and fearful. This classification is typically performed using supervised learning. Additionally, age estimation methods exist, among which the pixel-density-based approach is notable. This method assigns weights to influential facial regions to improve age prediction accuracy.

1-7 Research Method

At the beginning of the research, fundamental concepts essential for initiating work in this field are studied through reference books and relevant articles. Following this, a detailed examination of recent papers in the chosen domain is conducted to analyze specific details, strengths, and weaknesses of the subject. Finally, by implementing and testing various ideas presented in the literature, along with guidance from the advisor and incorporating original contributions, efforts are made to address the shortcomings of previous approaches and achieve the final results.

1-8 Research Structure

In the first chapter, the fundamental concepts, the necessity for conducting the research, and the problem statement are addressed. The second chapter presents the literature review, along with a discussion of certain foundational methods and algorithms. The third chapter provides a review of algorithms, previous works, and research related to the topic of this thesis, focusing on contributions made by other researchers up until the year 2017. The proposed methods and the process of constructing the proposed database, along with detailed explanations, will be introduced in the fourth chapter. Furthermore, in this chapter, both the visual and statistical results of existing methods and the proposed method will be evaluated using well-established databases as well as the newly proposed database. Finally, the fifth chapter summarizes the contents

of the thesis, draws conclusions based on the proposed methods, and provides recommendations for future research aimed at enhancing the proposed methods.

The chapters of this thesis are organized as follows:

- Chapter 1: This chapter discusses the basic concepts, the rationale for conducting the research, and the problem statement.
- Chapter 2: The literature review, along with an exploration of certain foundational methods and algorithms, is presented in this chapter.
- Chapter 3: This chapter reviews various algorithms, previous works, and research conducted by other researchers on the topic of this thesis, up until the year 2017.
- Chapter 4: The proposed methods and the detailed process for constructing the proposed database are discussed in this chapter.
- Chapter 5: In this chapter, the visual and statistical results of both existing methods and the proposed method are assessed using established databases as well as the proposed database.
- Chapter 6: This chapter offers a summary of the thesis, presents conclusions drawn from the proposed methods, and provides recommendations for future activities aimed at improving the proposed methods.

Chapter 2 Literature Review

2-1 Introduction

In this chapter, the literature review and some of the fundamental concepts required for the research are discussed. The use of sensors to capture signals that form the image of an object, which are then processed by a computer or other signal-processing devices to interpret and analyze the received signals, is known as machine vision. Machine vision, as an engineering tool, is applied in digital tools and computer networks to control other industrial instruments, such as robotic arms or extracting malfunctioning equipment. An image can be defined as a two-dimensional function $f(x, y)$, where x and y represent the spatial coordinates of the function, and the domain of f at each point of the coordinates x, y refers to the intensity or grayscale level of the image at that point. When x, y and the domain of f are restricted, the image is considered a digital image [2]. Image processing has two major branches: image enhancement and machine vision. Image enhancement includes methods such as using blur filters and contrast enhancement to improve the visual quality of images and ensure their proper display in the destination environment (e.g., printers or computer monitors). On the other hand, machine vision focuses on methods that allow us to understand the meaning and content of images, enabling their use in tasks such as robotics and image-based applications. Specifically, image processing refers to any type of signal processing when the input is an image, such as a photo or a scene from a video. The output of the image processor can either be an image or a set of specific signs or variables related to the image. Most image processing techniques involve treating the image as a two-dimensional signal and applying standard signal processing techniques to it. While image processing often refers to digital image processing, optical and analog image processing also exist.

2-2 Structured Light and Time of Flight Sensors

Scanning sensors operate by using a line of light to scan an entire object, either by moving the sensor or the object itself. To construct a three-dimensional model, all angles of the object must be exposed to the laser light of the scanning sensor. However, sensors such as structured light sensors and

time-of-flight (ToF) sensors do not require scanning or rotating the sensor or object. Instead, with each emitted light pulse, they capture the three-dimensional model of the area within the sensor's range [8]. These sensors were initially developed for non-military applications [9] and can cover distances ranging from a few centimeters to several kilometers. Additionally, they have the capability to capture up to 160 frames per second [10]. Time-of-flight sensors are highly useful in various applications, including packaging, labeling, detecting damaged objects in factories, patient monitoring in the medical field, security alerts in industrial environments, and navigation of industrial vehicles in narrow spaces. Figure 2–1 and Figure 2–2 are adapted from sources [11][12][13][14].

3D measuring technique	Time-of-flight	Stereo vision	Structured light
XY resolution	High	Scene dependant	Medium
Accuracy	Medium	Low	High
Software complexity	Low	High	Medium
Real-time-capability	High	Low	Medium
Material costs	Medium	Low	High
Low-light performance	Good	Weak	Good
Outdoor performance (Sunlight)	Medium	Good	Weak

Figure 2–1 Characteristics of depth sensors with different technologies

Component	V1	V2
Technique	Structured-light	Time-of-flight
Depth Sensor	1.8 to 3.5 m	1.3 to 3.5 m
IR Depth Image	320 x 240	512 x 424
Colour Image	640 x 480	1920 x 1080
Infra-red Image	no IR	512 x 424
Audio Stream	16 kHz, 16-bit	48 kHz, 16-bit
Field of View hor:	57 degrees	70 degrees
Field of View ver:	43 degrees	60 degrees
Minimum Latency	102 ms	20-60 ms

Figure 2–2 Differences between Kinect sensor version 1 and 2

2-3 Color, Grayscale, Depth, Thermal Images and 3D Models

The texture image or color image consists of three primary channels: red, green, and blue. Most early imaging sensors started their work with this format. However, to reduce the size of such images, an operation called image indexing can be used to decrease the image size and reduce the number of channels to just one. On the other hand, a grayscale image is a single-channel image represented as a two-dimensional matrix with values ranging from 0 to 255 for each pixel. The value 0 represents absolute black, 255 represents absolute white, and any number in between represents a shade of gray. Typically, for computational efficiency, color and texture images are converted to grayscale before processing. Depth images, captured by depth sensors such as Kinect, are often combined with texture images to enhance calculation accuracy or used independently. Due to their projection technology, depth sensors can operate in complete darkness, whereas texture sensors lack this capability. Thermal images are another type of depth image that function similarly to depth images. A three-dimensional model can also be generated from the captured depth image. Figure 2–3 illustrates the different types of these images.

Figure 2–3 From left to right (texture image, grayscale, depth, and thermal) [16]

Figure 2–4, from left to right, illustrates a two-dimensional grayscale image, a two-and-a-half-dimensional depth image, and a three-dimensional model extracted from the depth image. In the depth image, face detection has been performed using an elliptical fitting method for face extraction. The three-dimensional image has also been enhanced using reconstruction techniques. Figure 2–5 depicts the entire process of acquisition, reconstruction, facial rigging, and animation application to the three-dimensional model (from left to right).

Figure 2–4 From left to right (two-dimensional image, two-and-a-half-dimensional (depth) image, and three-dimensional image) [17]

Figure 2–5 From left to right (texture and depth data acquisition from Kinect, extracting a 3D model from depth data, applying animation to the model) [18]

2-4 Human and Face Detection

A human detection system refers to a system where the input is an image, and the output is the location of all humans present in that image. This system defines a region as output, which contains the human object. Over the past decade, the issue of human detection has attracted the attention of researchers in the fields of computer vision and pattern recognition. In visual content management, labeling is generally the main task. After labeling, operations such as annotation, search, and retrieval can be performed. In video surveillance, detecting, identifying, and monitoring humans in crowded and public scenes, such as airports, train stations, and supermarkets, is considered a key task. Human detection is also crucial in intelligent vehicles. Detecting pedestrians on the street to warn the driver about potential danger is an important application. Figure 2–6 shows some applications of human detection [19].

Figure 2–6 Applications of human detection include human motion detection, image and video retrieval, driver assistance systems, and surveillance systems [20].

Face detection is one of the most significant approaches facilitating human-machine interaction and an active field in computer vision. Identifying individuals from a predefined database has long been a key objective for any automated security system that operates without user intervention. The applications of such systems continue to expand with ongoing efforts to enhance security measures.

The first and most crucial step in face recognition is detecting the face in an image, as any error at this stage would prevent subsequent processes from executing correctly. In security systems (identity verification), the face’s position can be assumed to be fixed, meaning the user is required to position their face at a predetermined location under consistent lighting conditions. This eliminates the need to search for the face within an image, allowing the system to extract relevant sections from the input image and feed the detected face directly into the recognition system. Figure 2–7 illustrates examples of face detection, while [22] presents an instance of face recognition.

Figure 2-7 Examples of face detection [21]

2-5 Facial features

The human face plays an important role in people's lives and can be used to identify individuals from one another and obtain characteristics about age, race, personality, and emotional or affective states. In other words, these characteristics are divided into the following four categories:

1. Permanent facial features, such as bone structure, skin texture, and general facial characteristics. These features shape a person's unique appearance and are used for facial recognition.
2. Features that gradually bring changes to facial appearance, such as permanent wrinkles and changes in skin texture. These features can be used for age identification.
3. External facial features, such as glasses and cosmetic accessories. These features can provide additional information to help determine a person's gender.
4. Features that cause temporary changes in facial appearance due to facial muscle activity, leading to rapid changes in facial appearance.

The types of information obtained from the last category are divided into the following four categories:

- Attitudinal/emotional and psychological states (voluntary and involuntary facial expressions)

The importance of distinguishing between facial expressions that occur voluntarily and those that occur involuntarily becomes apparent when the

neurological layer for facial expressions is examined. In general, there are two neural pathways associated with facial expressions, each produced in a different area of the brain. Voluntary facial changes are generated in the cortical motor strip, whereas involuntary facial movements occur in the subcortical regions of the brain. The facial expressions produced by these two neural pathways differ in terms of which facial muscles are stimulated, as well as in the way they are activated and stimulated. For example, in involuntary facial expressions, muscle activity is smooth, coordinated, symmetrical, and consistent, whereas in voluntary expressions, muscle activity is less coordinated and involves irregular movements. The difference between these two types is the distinction between biologically driven stimuli and socially learned facial behaviors, which humans can acquire, similar to language, and consciously control in different situations. Most systems used for recognizing facial expressions are capable of detecting voluntary facial expressions, and very little effort has been made in recognizing involuntary facial expressions, except for a system that can distinguish between genuine and imitated pain expressions using eyebrow movements and parameters such as speed, intensity, and the duration required to produce that expression.

- Signals

Culture-specific communicative cues, such as winking.

- Involuntary actions

Such as yawning and biting the lips.

- Illustrators

Actions accompanying speech, such as raising the eyebrows.

- Regulators

Communication intermediaries such as changes in gaze direction, head movements, and smiling “[23], p. 4-5”.

- **Emotion recognition based on dynamic and flexible models**

Dynamic or adaptable models are those that can adjust according to the physical movements of the face. To achieve this adaptability, edge detectors are usually used to reveal movements. Although human faces exhibit significant diversity in appearance, there are notable commonalities in how facial elements change in response to emotional states. These methods operate based on defining facial action units, which are explained in the following sections.

Upper Face Action Units					
AU 1	AU 2	AU 4	AU 5	AU 6	AU 7
Inner Brow Raiser	Outer Brow Raiser	Brow Lowerer	Upper Lid Raiser	Cheek Raiser	Lid Tightener
*AU 41	*AU 42	*AU 43	AU 44	AU 45	AU 46
Lid Droop	Slit	Eyes Closed	Squint	Blink	Wink

Figure 2–8 Emotion recognition based on dynamic and flexible models [24]

- **Emotion recognition based on the contour strips model**

In models based on contour strips (thin line segments), a two-dimensional model of the face is defined based on specific facial points and their connections through line segments. As structural changes occur in the face, the length of these line segments changes in a way that ensures the model aligns appropriately with the new facial expression. Based on the changes in the base model, the new facial expression is extracted.

Figure 2–9 Emotion recognition based on the contour strips model [25]

- **Emotion recognition based on the point motion model**

The point motion model is one of the commonly used models in emotion recognition. In this model, a field of action is introduced in the image, and the movements related to it are extracted. Here, we face a nonlinear motion problem, which can be transformed into a linear problem by dividing it into smaller components. These movements are identified in a series of images belonging to a video sequence. The motion model can be designed in a two-dimensional or three-dimensional space, depending on the initial image [26], 1389, p. 5.

Figure 2–10 Emotion recognition based on the point motion model [27]

- **Emotion recognition based on edge and feature model**

The edge and feature-based model is one of the most efficient methods for motion detection in image sequences. In this method, the face is displayed as a frame-like form and is matched with each predefined frame model that has the best fit. This process is performed for each image in the sequence, and by comparing the extracted frames and their sequence, movements are detected. Figure 2–11 shows different facial expressions for the edge-feature model states. [26], 1389, p. 3.

Figure 2–11 The predefined frames in the edge-feature model [26], 1389, p. 3.

2-6 Facial Feature Detection Through Image Segmentation

Using image segmentation, facial elements can be identified and separated, and the geometric state of these elements can express the emotion or facial expression of the subject. For example, in Figure 2–12, facial features of two individuals in two different facial expressions are extracted.

Figure 2–12 Extraction of visual-muscular features of the face

2-7 Facial Feature Weighting for Effective Learning

After extracting facial features and for more effective learning, it is preferable to assign weights to the facial elements that have the most influence in expressing emotions and facial expressions. For example, in facial expression recognition, the muscles of the lips and eyes have the greatest impact on detection, while other muscles such as the forehead, temples, and cheeks have the least effect. Figure 2–13, with different coefficients for various facial regions, indicates their percentage impact on facial expressions. Additionally, Figure 2–14 shows how the mouth and eye features have been extracted from some samples of the Cohn-Kanade database [28] using the Viola and Jones algorithm.

Figure 2–13 Weighting Facial Features. Sample Image from the KDEF Database – Surprise Expression [29]

Figure 2–14 Extraction of Eye and Mouth Elements from Some Samples of the Cohn-Kanade Database [28]

2-8 Facial Expression Detection

So far, many researchers in the field of computer vision have proposed various methods to enable the automatic recognition of human facial expressions. Over the past decade, facial expression recognition has received significant attention in computer vision research. With the growing interest in human-machine interactive systems and applications that directly involve human interaction, the need to analyze messages conveyed through body movements and facial expressions has increased. Recognizing and analyzing emotional expressions is challenging because facial features vary from person to person and across different age groups. Additionally, its performance is influenced by the following three factors [30].

2-8-1 Gesture

When facial images are captured, the camera position may be frontal or from other angles. The face can also have different orientations, showing various perspectives of facial features, such as the nose or eyes, or it may be fully visible. One of the major challenges in image preprocessing is handling rotation and scalability.

Figure 2–15 Different poses of an image [29]

2-8-2 Occlusion

The face may be obstructed by objects and covered by glasses, masks, hair, or other elements. An example of this is shown in Figure 2–16. As a result, in this situation, feature extraction for emotion recognition becomes more complex.

Figure 2-16 Obstructed Image [31]

2-8-3 Illumination

If images are captured under different lighting conditions, the extracted features may be inaccurately identified. As a result, the speed of emotional state recognition decreases. In Figure 2-17, images have been taken under varying lighting conditions.

Figure 2-17 Different lighting conditions in the image [30].

This factor can make feature extraction more challenging. To neutralize the effects of lighting changes in an input image, image processing techniques such as histogram equalization and classification normalization before feature extraction are used.

There are different categorizations for works done in the field of facial expression analysis. Based on the type of input images, the works can be divided into two categories:

1. Analysis of still facial images
2. Analysis of dynamic facial images

Most of the presented analysis systems either work only on still images or only on dynamic images. However, an ideal system should be capable of analyzing both scenarios.

2-9 Emotional Expression Detection Methodology

Facial emotional expression detection consists of three primary steps. In the first step, the input image is obtained, and the facial region is identified. Following this, the image undergoes pre-processing, where its size and intensity are normalized. In the second step, emotional features are extracted from the image or a sequence of images. Finally, in the third step, the extracted features are classified based on predefined rules. The results of the third step determine the specific emotional state.

Thus, an effective recognition system should meet the following objectives:

- Generate realistic expressions
- Operate in real-time
- Ensure sufficient automation
- Easily adapt to the individual's face
- Be capable of working with both video fields and images of various resolutions
- Be resilient to various lighting conditions
- Detect involuntary emotional expressions
- Do not require mandatory pre-processing of images and video fields
- Detect emotional states despite any occlusions in the image
- Function effectively across diverse cultures and skin tones
- Accurately detect emotional expressions from frontal, profile, or intermediate angles of the face

The image can be represented in three distinct ways:

1. The first method treats the entire image as a comprehensive representation.
2. The second method represents the image as a collection of features, which is known as analytical representation.
3. The third method is a combination of the two previously mentioned methods, referred to as the hybrid method.

The prominent facial features include the eyebrows, eyes, mouth, and nose. Emotional states arise from temporary deformations in these facial features. In still images, the feature extraction process involves localizing the face and its features within the scene. In the case of a sequence of images, feature extraction refers to tracking the face and its features throughout the scene. The method of facial representation and the type of input image dictate the feature extraction mechanism. In Figure 2–18, seven primary facial expressions are displayed in texture image format (top row) and 3D model format (bottom row).

Figure 2–18 The seven main facial expressions in the form of texture images and 3D models [32].

2-10 Facial Micro-Expression recognition

The estimated duration of a facial expression ranges between 0.5 to 4 seconds, while a micro-expression lasts between 0.1 to 0.5 seconds. Additionally, some references mention durations of $1/3$, $1/15$, and $1/25$ of a second. Naturally, capturing micro-expressions requires recording video frames at a rate of 30 to 60 frames per second. Computationally, facial expression recognition methods can be used to detect micro-expressions.

Figure 2-19 Micro-expression of sadness [33]

The action units used for Figure 2-19 are 4+9+17, which indicate a sense of disgust. Figure 2-20 illustrates the facial muscle changes in the micro-expression of disgust.

Figure 2-20 Micro-expression of disgust [34]

2-11 Facial Action Coding System

The best standard for classifying facial muscle movements to express facial emotions was introduced by Ekman and Friesen as the Facial Action Coding System (FACS). They defined a set of action units (AUs) by breaking down each complex movement into a series of fundamental movements. In this system, each action unit is independent and indivisible. The proposed system automatically tracks facial features, detects their changes, categorizes them into FACS codes, and interprets them as emotions with specific intensity levels. It also identifies multiple simultaneous emotions while eliminating potential contradictions. The Facial Action Coding System has been the foundation for most automated or semi-automated facial expression recognition studies. The first coding system was introduced in 1978, comprising 44 action units numbered from 1 to 46. Over time, researchers refined this system, and by 2002, the number of action units had increased to 51 or more, incorporating eye

movements. In this classification, units numbered 1 to 7 correspond to the upper half of the face, while the remaining units relate to the lower half—"Ekman, Friesen, 1987." A selection of these units is presented in the table below. **Error! Reference source not found.** provides details on some of these action units.

Table 2-1 Facial Action Units in FACS

کد	توصیف	کد	توصیف
۱	انتهای درونی ابرو بالا رفته است.	۱۸	لبها جمع و گرد شده‌اند.
۲	انتهای بیرونی ابرو بالا رفته است.	۲۰	طول دهان بزرگتر شده است.
۳	ابرو پایین‌تر آمده است.	۲۳	لبها به هم فشرده شده‌اند.
۵	پلک بالایی، بالاتر رفته است.	۲۴	گوشه لبها بالاتر رفته است.
۶	گونه بالاتر رفته است.	۲۵	لبها از هم جدا شده‌اند.
۷	پلک، تنگتر شده است.	۲۶	فک پایین‌تر آمده است.
۹	بینی، چروک شده است.	۲۷	دهان کاملاً باز شده است.
۱۰	لب بالا، بالاتر رفته است.	۲۸	لبها مکیده شده‌اند.
۱۱	بینی فشرده‌تر شده است.	۴۱	پلک بالاکمی افتاده است.
۱۲	طول لب بزرگتر شده است.	۴۲	پلک بالا افتاده است.
۱۶	لب پایین منقبض شده است.	۴۳	چشم کاملاً بسته است.
۱۷	چانه بالا آمده است.	۴۴	چشم ظاهراً بسته است.

Comparison of methods based on action units should consider specific limitations. The database used, image quality, lighting conditions, number of test images, computational complexity, and the number of selected action units are among the most significant limitations. Additionally, the realism of the images is crucial, as only a few databases have been collected in real-world conditions. Since multiple classes are involved, accurate classification is essential. If an image sequence is misclassified, the incorrect categorization must also be considered. For instance, misidentifying a happy expression as surprised is significantly different from misidentifying it as sad, as happiness and surprise share more similarities than happiness and sadness. Figure 2–21 illustrates expressions of surprise, happiness, sadness, and anger, which are formed by the following combinations of action units:

- **Surprise** = 1 + 2 + 5 + 25 + 26
- **Happiness** = 6 + 12

- **Sadness** = 1 + 15 + 17
- **Anger** = 4 + 7 + 9 + 10 + 25

Figure 2–21 Action Units of Surprise, Happiness, Sadness, and Anger [37]

2-12 landmark Localization

Various facial annotation methods are used for tracking and recognizing facial expressions based on statistical and geometric appearance. Figure 2–22 illustrates different facial annotation methods, while Figure 2–23 depicts annotation using the AAM method.

Figure 2-22 Types of landmark Localization [38]

2-12-1 Active Appearance Model

Figure 2-23 An Example of Landmark Localization Using the Active Appearance Model (AAM) [39]

This method is a statistical approach to fitting an appearance model to a new image, based on a number of key points marked on the sensitive regions of the image. Geometric feature-based methods represent the shape and location of facial components (such as the mouth, eyes, eyebrows, and nose). Features of

these components or key points are extracted to form a feature vector, revealing the geometry of the face. The main focus of these methods is on the movement and positioning of the mentioned points in different facial expressions. To improve the accuracy of these methods, selecting the precise location of the key facial points is crucial, and in real-time applications, the speed of point selection becomes an issue. Various methods have been proposed for this purpose, with one of the best being the Active Appearance Models (AAM) [41] [40] [39].

2-12-2 Active Shape Model

It is a statistical model that iteratively adjusts the annotations until the model is fully fitted onto the object. The iterative process for fitting the model to the image works by selecting and updating the closest point to each annotation or key point based on the area. The problem with this approach is the need for large training data and the necessity to construct the labeling steps for the images. However, its advantages include high accuracy and insensitivity to noise. The difference between the Active Appearance Model (AAM) and the shape model is that the AAM attempts to optimize the model-image differences instead of locally fitting each point iteratively. After placing the model in the image, the difference between the model and the image is calculated and then the model is updated. The advantages of the AAM method include high efficiency and precise alignment. However, this method faces challenges with complex backgrounds and may update the model based on background objects as well [42]. Figure 2–24 and Figure 2–25 illustrate the shape model and facial landmarking.

Figure 2–24 The process method of the Active shape model [43]

Figure 2–25 Annotation by the Active shape model method [44]

2-13 Feature Detection

Local features and local descriptors, which represent the vectorized local neighbors, are considered fundamental concepts in machine vision algorithms. Their applications include image registration, object detection, classification, object tracking, and slow-motion estimation; but what kind of features are local features? Local features refer to patterns or structures that appear distinctly, such as points, edges, and patches in a digital image. What a feature truly represents is not important, and the key point is the difference it has with the surrounding environment at those points. Local features are detected and represented in the form of bubble-shaped pixels, corner pixels, and edges pixels. Local features allow the discovery of relationships within the image regardless of occlusion, changes in viewpoint, or distortion of the image.

Now, we need to answer the question of what factors make a suitable local feature. In response, it should be said that feature detectors based on image gradients or changes in the intensity of grayscale levels typically form the best

local features. These features include edges, blobs, and regions. A suitable local feature should possess the following characteristics:

- **Detection or recognition of repeated patterns:**
If two images that are very similar are given to the system, the system should be able to detect both differences and similarities. This can be done by changing the viewpoint.
- **Distinctness:**
The neighborhood around the center of the feature should change enough to allow for an acceptable comparison between features.
- **Localization:**
The feature should have a unique and specific position. Changes in viewpoint should not affect the final output.

Feature detection means selecting a region of the image that contains specific content, such as corners and blobs. By marking these regions, conditions for further processing can be prepared. This does not mean that these features are necessarily the corners of tables; rather, points from the image are chosen that, under different image conditions such as rotation or viewpoint change, remain unchanged and can be selected again under any circumstance. There are various methods for feature detection, which will be explained further, but the choice of feature detector entirely depends on the nature of the data and the field of its use. For example, in cases where the goal is to detect bacterial cells, choosing a blob detector is better than choosing a corner detector. If the image concerns a human face and involves many complex visual features, selecting a point-based detector, such as the SURF local feature detector, is a suitable option. In Figure 2–26, we observe different methods for detecting features: blob detection, region-based feature detection, and corner detection (from left to right) using various local feature detection methods.

Figure 2–26 Different methods of feature detection

In global features, an image is represented by a multidimensional feature vector in order to describe the entire image. In other words, global features consist of a feature vector that calculates values for various aspects of the image. These aspects include concepts such as color, texture, and the shape of objects in the image. In practice, after extraction, a specific feature vector can be compared with its counterpart in another image. For example, if we want to differentiate between the sea (blue) and the forest (green) using global features, the color aspects of each must be completely distinguishable. Therefore, global features related to the characteristics of the image are examined based on all pixels, and feature selection will be made based on the examination of all pixels. These characteristics can include color, texture, histogram, edge, or even the results of a filter applied to the entire image [46] [45].

Figure 2–27 Local features (on the right) versus global features (on the left) [46]

2-14 Feature Extraction

Computations that occur in the region of discovered features by the feature interpreter, in order to extract useful and meaningful information, are called feature extraction, which takes place after the feature detection stage. The feature extraction problem involves converting the compressed feature

detection matrix into a vector, usually normalized, to facilitate the learning and classification process. There are various and diverse algorithms for extracting features from an image, each of which has its own specific efficiency and is selected based on the type of problem. Some of these algorithms and methods will be explained below [48] [47].

2-15 Feature Description

A feature descriptor is an algorithm whose goal is to extract a feature vector from a selected feature matrix. The feature descriptor encodes interesting information in the form of a set of numbers. For example, in face detection or recognition, specific features obtained in the stages of feature detection and extraction are encoded in a way that can be later utilized. In general, the described features are not different under different image conditions, and images with altered states, such as rotated images, can also be used. For example, the SIFT algorithm encodes the local gradient information of neighboring pixels into a feature vector. Additionally, the SURF and HOG algorithms are also considered feature descriptors. Essentially, a feature descriptor is a representation of the image that simplifies the image by extracting useful information and discarding unnecessary data [51] [50] [49]."

2-16 Feature Vector

After the stages of detection, extraction, and description of features by the respective algorithms in each method, we will have a feature vector of size $1 \times n$ for each sample from the database or data, representing the final characteristics processed by previous algorithms. This vector, if there is no need for dimensionality reduction or feature selection, is ready for learning and classification by the respective algorithms. This vector may be used in a weighted form, for example, in linear regression. The feature vector is usually used for supervised learning and is applicable in nearly all fields of machine vision and statistical pattern recognition.

2-17 Feature Selection or Dimensionality Reduction

As explained in the feature vector section, the meaningful final output from an image is called the feature vector; and as we know, this vector has a size of $1 \times n$. However, the variable n does not always have a small and normal value,

and depending on the size of the image and the feature extraction algorithm, it can even reach millions for each sample (especially in signal processing). Given the processing power of today's systems, processing just one sample with millions of values is not problematic. But what happens if we face a database? With the advancement of home computers and laptops and consequently the transformation of computing systems in terms of both variety and execution power, for example, depth sensors like Kinect are constantly improving in terms of hardware power. Thus, it can be said that the output of these sensors is also of high quality, requiring stronger processors and more processing. In the field of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in software engineering, to validate a new algorithm or any combination of algorithms, that method must be validated with various databases to ensure the scientific quality of the effect. In image databases (in this case, face images), there are usually many samples, and if these samples are captured by powerful sensors, the need for processing increases as well. When depth sensors like Kinect are mentioned, we are actually considering two types of output: the texture or color image and the depth image. This results in a twofold increase in the final processing because we are dealing with two types of data from the same scene. On the other hand, with the rapid advancement of science, especially in feature extraction methods, researchers are opting for computationally heavy but precise methods to improve the final algorithm's accuracy, which will also increase the amount of computation. In such cases, the feature vector output, obtained from the feature extraction process, can become very large. Also, when dealing with a database, depending on the size of the database, these computations increase exponentially. For example, if we have a database of images with a size of $512 * 512$ for each depth image, and the database contains 5000 images for all the samples, and we are using a very heavy feature extraction algorithm for computation, then the feature vector for each image might reach $10000 * 1$, which would make learning and classification extremely difficult even with today's powerful systems. In such cases, feature selection or dimensionality reduction algorithms come into play, reducing these large vectors from hundreds of thousands to only a thousand or a few hundred. Interestingly, this process, performed by optimized algorithms

like regularization, results in the loss of very little information, less than 1%, while reducing the computational load by thousands of times.

Feature selection or dimensionality reduction methods consider the dependencies between features in each column of the output feature vector matrix and select the best features that have the most impact on learning and classification, discarding the rest, which is usually the majority of the data. However, as mentioned, if we choose an appropriate feature selection method, this reduction in data volume won't significantly impact the accuracy of the final output. There are many traditional methods for this purpose, but the selection method must be based on the number of samples or rows in the feature matrix and the volume or columns of the feature matrix. For instance, one of the traditional feature selection or dimensionality reduction methods is Principal Component Analysis (PCA), which has low computational speed but good performance, though the data loss may be high. Another newer method is sequential feature selection, which is not suitable for large feature matrices but works better than PCA for small matrices. But what if our data is large? In this regard, methods like elastic nets and Lasso were invented, which revolutionized feature selection algorithms. We use the Lasso method in this study. This method is explained in detail in the proposed methods section.

Since you are busy, you can only spend a limited amount of time each day with your robot, showing it things and labeling them. However, the robot is on and receiving a lot of data throughout the day. Here, the robot can learn unsupervised by itself and also use the experiences when you guide it to learn more effectively. The combination of both unlabeled data and labeled data used by the intelligent agent is called semi-supervised learning."

2-18 Conclusion

In the previous chapter, a review of some key concepts necessary for presenting the research background and implementing the proposed methods was conducted. Topics including face and facial expression recognition, texture and depth image sensors, fundamental concepts of image processing and its applications, as well as the core principles of machine learning and pattern

recognition were examined. This literature review contributes to a better progression of the following chapters.

Chapter 3 Research background

3-1 Introduction

This chapter reviews the background of research conducted in areas related to the proposed methods. The topics discussed in this study and presented in the chapter on proposed methods, whose historical background is examined in this chapter, include:

- Database construction
- Face detection and extraction
- Age estimation
- Gender recognition
- Facial expression and micro-expression recognition

3-2 Database (Background)

For the evaluation of scientific research, an appropriate database in the relevant research field is required to assess the proposed method in terms of speed and accuracy. A database designed for identifying the identities of individuals within it and evaluating the recognition capability of the proposed algorithm is referred to as a face recognition database. These databases are typically sampled under various conditions, including environmental lighting, horizontal and vertical face rotation, the presence of glasses, and facial hair. An algorithm or system that maintains high classification accuracy under different conditions is considered effective. A database that contains samples of individuals' faces with various facial expressions—such as neutral, smiling, angry, sad, surprised, disgusted, and fearful—is known as a facial expression recognition database. Similar to face recognition databases, these databases may also be sampled under diverse conditions. Due to the variety of facial samples they contain, they can also be used for face recognition. If data collection is performed in video frames at a minimum rate of 30 frames per second, the database can also be used for micro-expression recognition. Given that this study involves constructing a database for face recognition, expression recognition, and micro-expression detection using the Kinect v2 sensor, it is

essential to review previous research in this area. The following section introduces some of these databases.

3-2-1 Texture-Only Database

For facial and expression recognition, various databases exist. First, we will review some well-known texture-based databases. Since the primary focus of this study is facial and expression recognition using both texture and depth data, we will examine both texture-only and texture-depth databases. Table 3- 1 presents two examples of databases used in this research.

Table 3- 1 Specifications of Texture-Only Databases

نام پایگاه داده	تعداد نمونه‌ها	حس‌گر	کاربرد	نوع داده	ابعاد تصویر	حالات چهره	سال	حجم	استناد تا ۲۰۱۷	ارجاع
JAFFE	۱۰	-	تشخیص چهره و حالات آن	۲۱۲ تصویر خاکستری	۲۵۶*۲۵۶	۷ حالت اصلی	۱۹۹۸	۱۱ مگابایت	۱۳۴۸	[۵۵]
KDEF	۷۰-۳۵ مرد و ۳۵ زن- بین ۲۰ تا ۳۰ سال	Pentax LX	تشخیص چهره و حالات آن	۵۰۴۱ تصویر رنگی	۵۶۲*۷۶۲	۷ حالت اصلی	۱۹۹۸	۵۰۰ مگابایت	۱۶۲۴	[۲۹]

Figure 3-1 Examples from the JAFFE Database [55]

Figure 3-2 Examples from the KDEF Database [29]

3-2-2 Texture-Depth Databases

This type of databases, in addition to texture images, also contain depth images that have been captured using depth sensors. Their volume and quality are significantly higher than depth-only databases, and due to having a depth dimension, they contain more details for analysis. Because these types of

databases are novel, their number and the number of citations to them are low. Table 3-2 introduces several facial expression recognition databases that include both texture and depth images and are intended for use in this research. In the following, we will observe samples of texture-depth databases used in this research in two forms: texture images and depth images. Additionally, one of the databases, besides texture and depth images, also includes thermal images.

Table 3-2 Specifications of Texture-Depth Databases

نام پایگاه داده	تعداد نمونه-ها	حسگر	کاربرد	نوع داده	ابعاد تصویر	حالات چهره	سال	حجم	استناد تا ۲۰۱۷	ارجاع
Eurecom Kinect Face	۵۲-۱۴ مؤنث و ۳۸ مذکر	Kinect V.1	تشخیص چهره و حالات آن	۱۲۴۸ تصاویر رنگی بافت و عمق	RGB= ۲۵۶*۲۵۶ Depth= ۲۵۶*۲۵۶	۳ حالت- خنثی، متعجب و خوشحال	۲۰۱۴	۵۰۰ مگابایت	۶۷	[۳۱]
VAP RGB-D Face	۱۳	Kinect V.1	تشخیص چهره و حالات آن	۲۹۶۰ تصاویر رنگی بافت و عمق	RGB= ۳۵۱*۴۲۱ Depth= ۴۸۰*۶۴۰	۵ حالت- خنثی، خوشحال، متعجب، خشم، غم	۲۰۱۲	۶ گیگابایت	۵۱	[۵۶]
VAP RGB-D-T Face	۵۱	Kinect V.1 And AXIS Q1922	تشخیص چهره و حالات آن	۴۶۳۶۰ تصاویر رنگی بافت و عمق و گرمایی	RGB= ۴۸۰*۶۴۰ Depth= ۴۸۰*۶۴۰ Thermal= ۲۸۸*۳۸۴	۴ حالت- خنثی، خوشحال، متعجب، خشم	۲۰۱۴	۱/۳ گیگابایت	۶	[۵۷]
Curtin Face	۲۵	Kinect V.1	تشخیص چهره و حالات آن	۵۰۰۰ تصاویر رنگی بافت و عمق	RGB= ۴۸۰*۶۴۰ Depth= ۴۸۰*۶۴۰	۷ حالت اصلی	۲۰۱۳	۱۲ گیگابایت	۱۳۸	[۵۸]
FEEDB	۵۰	Kinect V.1	تشخیص چهره و حالات آن	فریم ویدیویی- ۳۰ فریم آن	RGB= ۴۸۰*۶۴۰ Depth= ۴۸۰*۶۴۰	۳۳ حالت چهره	۲۰۱۳	۱۰۰ گیگابایت- ۴۰ گیگابایت استفاده شده.	۱۲	[۵۹]
Face Grabber	۴۰-۳۳ مذکر و ۷ مؤنث	Kinect V.2	تشخیص چهره و حالات آن	۶۷۱۵۹ تصاویر رنگی بافت و عمق	RGB= ۲۰۸۰*۱۹۲۰ Depth= ۴۲۴*۵۱۲	۷ حالت اصلی	۲۰۱۶	۸/۵ گیگابایت	۲	[۶۰]

Figure 3–3 Samples from the Eurecom Kinect Face Database [31]

Figure 3–4 Samples from the VAP RGB-D Face Database [56]

Figure 3–5 Samples from the VAP RGB-D-T Face Database [57]

Figure 3-6 Samples from the Curtin Face Database [58]

Figure 3-7 Samples from the FEEDB Database [59]

Figure 3-8 Samples from the Face Grabber Database [60]

3-3 Face Detection and Extraction (Background)

As mentioned in the literature review chapter, face detection refers to identifying the face object from other objects within a digital image in such a way that it can be extracted from the image.

3-3-1 Face Detection Using Real-time Robust Object Detection

Face detection is a computer technology aimed at determining the position and size of human faces in digital images. This technology detects human faces and ignores other objects such as trees, buildings, etc. This technique plays a crucial role in many machine vision applications, such as face recognition, human target tracking, biometrics, and high-level applications like robotic vision. The method was first published by Paul Viola and Michael Jones in 2001 and 2004 [61][62] and is commonly referred to as the Viola-Jones method.

This method uses four key components:

- Simple rectangular features, known as Haar features [63]
- Integral images for fast feature evaluation
- AdaBoost machine learning method for feature selection [63]
- A cascade classifier for quickly rejecting non-face windows

Viola and Jones used a technique called integral images to determine which of the hundreds of Haar features exist in each image. For selecting a specific Haar feature to use, they employed a machine learning method called AdaBoost. The AdaBoost method combines many weak classifiers to create a strong classifier. Viola and Jones combined a series of AdaBoost classifiers into a filter chain. Each filter is an AdaBoost classifier made up of several weak classifiers. If any of these filters fail to accept an image region as a face, that region is immediately classified as non-face. When a filter accepts a region as a face, the region passes into the next filter in the chain. If the region successfully passes through all the filters in the chain, it is classified as a face. Figure 3–9 shows an example of face detection using the Viola-Jones algorithm applied to both texture and depth images. This method is specifically designed for texture images but works reasonably well on depth images as well. In this research, this

method will be used to extract faces from texture images. Additionally, the algorithm has been effectively used for face detection in [72].

Figure 3-9 Application of the Viola-Jones method on a number of texture and depth images for face detection [64]

3-2-2 Face Detection Using Elliptical Fitting

Another face detection method in digital images is ellipse fitting, which is highly practical. In this method, an elliptical geometric shape is aligned with elements within the plane, and objects resembling an ellipse are extracted. Image 3.10 shows an example of face detection using this method, where, from left to right and top to bottom, the elliptical shape is first fitted to the face, then rotated upright, and the face is cropped [65]. In this research, this method will be used to develop a technique for extracting faces from depth images.

Figure 3-10 Face detection using the ellipse fitting method [65]

3-3-3 Face Detection Through 3D Face Model Fitting Using Segmentation

This method was proposed by Frank B. ter Haar and Remco C. Veltkamp. In this method, the pixel at the tip of the nose closest to the sensor is identified, and then the image is segmented to a certain threshold [66]. Figure 3–11 illustrates this process. Additionally, the method of face detection and extraction using skin color is highly effective in texture images [67]. Furthermore, a method for face detection and extraction from depth images is presented in Chapter Four, which combines this method with the ellipse fitting method and a standard deviation filter for detecting and extracting faces from depth images.

Figure 3–11 Face detection from depth image by image segmentation.

3-4 Age Estimation (Background)

The process of using statistical pattern recognition and processing techniques to assess facial muscles (in terms of sagging muscles) is called age estimation. As the name of this method suggests, an exact and precise value for a person's age will not be provided, but only an estimate of it with a certain margin of error. The reason for this is that, in such situations, there are often unlabeled data, making it an unsupervised task. Since we have presented a method for age estimation in Chapter 4, we will review the work done in this area.

3-4-1 Age Estimation Based on Age Patterns

In this method, first, images of different samples from the age database are provided to the system in a supervised manner, and learning is performed using various techniques. Then, the built model is tested with new data. For example, in 2007, Xin Geng and Zhi-Hua Zhou designed a system where the system would

start training the model by receiving a specific number of images of individuals at various ages, and this model was tested with new data to calculate its error [68]. Figure 3.12 shows the age pattern vector in this method, where the x-axis represents the age of individuals. Additionally, Figure 3.13 shows two samples from the FG-NET database [69] at different ages, displayed in two rows for training. They used PCA features and an SVM classifier to evaluate their method.

Figure 3–12 Age pattern vectors [68]

Figure 3–13 Two samples of individuals from the FG-NET database in two rows and at different ages [68]

3-5 Gender Detection (Background)

Gender recognition in computer systems refers to the ability to distinguish between the two classes, male and female, from a set of training and testing images. The following sections will describe several examples of this process applied to texture-depth databases.

3-5-1 Gender Detection with 3D LBP Gradient Descriptor for Depth Images

In 2012, Huynh, Tri achieved a recognition accuracy of 87.48% on the Eurecom Kinect database [31] using Gradient-LBP features and an SVM classifier [70].

3-5-2 Using Kinect Data for Gender, Ethnicity and Identity Detection

In 2015, Elhocine developed a gender recognition system using LBP, LPQ, HOG, and BSIF features along with an SVM classifier. They achieved satisfactory results on the Curtin Face database [58], which is a texture-depth database. For example, using the BSIF feature, they obtained a recognition accuracy of 87.7% for texture data and 85.2% for depth data [71].

3-5-3 Using Kinect Data for Gender, Ethnicity and Identity Detection (Second Method)

Additionally, in the same year, these two researchers developed a gender recognition system for the Curtin Face database [58]. Using the HOG feature and an AdaBoost SVM classifier, they achieved a recognition accuracy of 86.8% for texture data and 85% for depth data. More detailed information can be found in Table 3.1 [71].

3-6 Facial Expression Detection (Background)

Facial expression recognition was thoroughly explained in the previous two chapters. However, in summary, recognizing a person's inner emotions based on the form and appearance of their facial muscles is referred to as facial expression recognition or emotion recognition. Conceptually, emotion recognition and facial expression recognition are essentially the same, as even a congenitally blind person displays their emotions on their face in the same way as a sighted individual. The following section introduces some of the latest research in this field.

3-6-1 Using RGB-D Database for Face and Expression Detection

In 2012, Hg RI and Jasek P achieved a recognition accuracy of 92.88% on the VAP-RGBD database [56]. They used the PCA method for feature extraction and classification [56]. The number of classes in this database is limited to only five. Table 3.3 provides comprehensive information about this database.

3-6-2 Emotion Detection Using Depth Data

In 2015, Mr. Szwoch, who is also the creator of the FEEDB database [59], achieved a recognition accuracy of only 50% using nine facial expression classes and just 25 training samples. He employed local features and the KNN classifier for this task. It is worth mentioning that this database, collected using Kinect version 1, has various reception issues [73].

3-6-3 Expression Detection Based on LPQ+es-LBP-s Method

In 2015, Wei-Lun Chao focused on improving the recognition accuracy of a well-known texture-based database called JAFFE [55] and successfully achieved this goal. This database contains seven primary facial expression classes. He utilized LPQ+ (es-LBP) features along with an SVM classifier, achieving a recognition accuracy of 94.88% [74].

3-6-4 Expression Detection Using Hidden Markov Model

Additionally, in 2016, Zineb Elgarrari achieved a recognition accuracy of 88.6% on the KDEF database [29]. She used Gabor filter features and an HMM classifier to classify the seven primary facial expression classes. Furthermore, she applied the Fisher Analysis method for dimensionality reduction [75].

3-6-5 Face and Expression Detection Using Texture-Depth-Thermal Images

In 2016, Oliu Simon and Marc utilized LBP+Harr+HOG features, known as the HOGOM method, and the WNNC2 classifier to achieve a recognition accuracy of 95.7% on the VAP RGBDT database [57], which is a texture-depth-thermal database.

3-6-6 Automatic Emotion Detection Based on Eye Region Changes

In 2016, M achieved recognition accuracies of 96.6% and 96.63% on the Cohn-Kanade [76] and FG-NET [69] databases, respectively, by applying the Gabor Filter feature to the eye region and using the SVM classifier [77]. They

first converted video frames into images, then used the Viola and Jones object detection method to extract the eye regions. They applied the Gabor filter feature to these regions, calculated the eye area, and combined these features with the previously obtained ones. These features were then fed into the SVM learning and classification process for seven main facial expression classes.

3-6-7 Expression Detection Using EEPP Method

In 2017, Mao designed a system for facial expression recognition that used the EEPP feature and classifier along with the Face Grabber database [60]. In the single-face scenario, they achieved a recognition accuracy of 83% for the seven main facial expressions.

Table 3- 3 The results obtained by other researchers on the databases used in this research.

نام پایگاه داده	پژوهشگر و سال پژوهش	ویژگی (ها)	کلاسه بند	دقت	کارکرد	توضیحات	ارجاع
JAFFE	Wei-LunChao ۲۰۱۵	LPQ+ (es-LBP)	SVM	۹۴/۸۸	تشخیص حالات چهره	expression specific local binary pattern	[۷۴]
KDEF	Elgarrai, Zineb ۲۰۱۶	Gabor Filter	HMM	۸۸/۶	تشخیص حالات چهره	کاهش ابعاد Fisher's Analysis	[۷۵]
FG-NET	Xin Geng, et. al ۲۰۰۷	PCA	SVM	۹۳/۲۳	تخمین سن	-	[۶۸]
Eurecom Kinect Face	Huynh, Tri ۲۰۱۲	Gradient-LBP	SVM	۸۷/۱۸	تشخیص جنسیت	LBP= ۷۸/۸۵ 3D-LBP= ۸۵/۹۰	[۷۰]
	Ijjina, Earnest Paul ۲۰۱۴	CNN	CNN	۸۷/۹	تشخیص حالات چهره	-	[۷۸]
VAP RGB-D Face	Hg RI, Jasek P ۲۰۱۲	PCA	PCA	۹۲/۸۸	تشخیص حالات چهره	-	[۵۶]
VAP RGB-D-T Face	Oliu Simon, Marc ۲۰۱۶	LBP+Haar+Hog	Weighted Nearest Neighbour Classifier (WNNC)	۹۵/۷	تشخیص حالات چهره	LBP+Haar+Hog= HOGOM	[۵۷]
Curtin Face	ElhocineBoutellaa ۲۰۱۵	HOG	Ada boost SVM	RGB= ۸۶/۸ Depth= ۸۵/۰	تشخیص جنسیت	With LPQ RGB= ۸۵/۳ Depth= ۸۳/۵	[۷۱]
FEEDB	Mariusz Szwoch ۲۰۱۵	Local Features	KNN	۵۰/۰	تشخیص حالات چهره	استفاده از ۲۵ نمونهی پایگاه داده و ۹ حالت چهره.	[۷۳]
Face Grabber	Sen Yuan, Xia Mao ۲۰۱۷	exponential elastic preserving projections (EEPP),	exponential elastic preserving projections (EEPP),	۸۳/۰	تشخیص حالات چهره	تکچهره	[۷۹]

Table 3- 3 displays the results of various activities conducted on the introduced databases (as mentioned above). The aim is to present the best, most reliable, and up-to-date results to improve the recognition accuracy. These activities span various areas such as age estimation, gender recognition, and facial expression recognition. All the activities outlined in Chapter 5 will be performed on these databases, including the proposed database, and selectively. Additionally, some activities that have not been conducted on these databases before will be carried out for the first time in this research. This table includes the aforementioned results along with additional explanations.

3-7 Micro-Expression Detection (Background)

As previously mentioned, the estimated duration for a facial expression to occur ranges from 0.5 to 4 seconds, while micro-expressions last between 0.1 to 0.5 seconds. In some references, these durations are also stated as 1/3, 1.5, and 2.5 seconds. It is evident that to capture micro-expressions, receiving video frames at a rate of 30 to 200 frames per second is essential. No RGB-D or texture-depth database specifically for micro-expression recognition has been released so far. Therefore, no research has been conducted in a texture-depth format; however, a few databases and studies have been presented for texture-only images aimed at recognizing micro-expressions. We will discuss these studies. It is important to note that this research will only utilize texture-depth databases, some examples of which have been provided, for evaluating proposed methods. The following review serves only informational purposes (except for the CASME database). Table 3- 4 presents the characteristics of several texture-only micro-expression databases, while Table 3- 5 shows the results of other studies on these texture-only databases.

Figure 3–14 displays examples of micro-expressions and the related motion units extracted from the CASME database [103].

Table 3- 4 Characteristics of some texture-only micro-expression databases

نام پایگاه داده	تعداد نمونه‌ها	حسگر	کاربرد	نوع داده	ابعاد تصویر	حالات چهره	سال	استناد	ارجاع
SMIC	۱۶	PixelINK PL-B774U	تشخیص ریز حالات چهره	۱۶۴ فایل بافت ویدیویی (۱۰۰ فریم)	۶۴۰*۴۸۰	۴ ریز حالت	۲۰۱۳	۹۳	[۱۰۲]

CASME	۱۹	BenQ M31 GRAS-03K2C	تشخیص ریز حالات چهره	۱۹۵ فایل بافت ویدیویی (۶۰ فریم)	۶۴۰*۴۸۰ ۱۲۸۰*۷۸۰	۷ ریزحالت اصلی	۲۰۱۳	۸۳	[۱۰۳]
Polikovsky's	۱۰	Grasshopper	تشخیص ریز حالات چهره	۴۲ فایل ویدیویی بافت (۲۰۰ فریم)	۶۴۰*۴۸۰	۱۳ ریزحالت	۲۰۰۹	۱۰۲	[۱۰۴]
USF-HD	۱۰۰	-	تشخیص حالات و ریز حالات چهره	۵۶ فایل ویدیویی بافت (۳۰ فریم)	۱۲۸۰*۷۸۰	۶ ریزحالت	۲۰۱۱	۹۱	[۱۰۵]
YorkDDT	۹	-	تشخیص ریز حالات چهره	(۳۰ فریم)	۶۴۰*۴۸۰	۱۸ ریزحالت	۲۰۰۹	۱۳۰	[۱۰۹]

Table 3- 5 The results of other researchers on texture-only micro-expression recognition databases presented in Table 3-4

نام پایگاه داده	پژوهشگر و سال پژوهش	ویژگی (ها)	کلاسه بند	دقت	توضیحات	ارجاع
Polikovsky's	S Polikovsky ۲۰۰۹-	3D-Gradients orientation histogram		۸۰٪	نتایج بر اساس عناصر چهره و جداگانه بدمست آمده و میانگین گرفته شده.	[۱۰۴]
YorkDDT SMIC	T Pfister ۲۰۱۱-	LBP-TOP	Multiple Kernel Learning (MKL)	%۷۱/۵ %۷۱/۴	هم SVM, RF با کلاسه بندهای تست شده و نتایج ضعیفتری نشان داده است.	[۱۰۶]
Cohn and Kanade's (CK)	Wu, Qi ۲۰۱۱-	Gabor Filter	Gentle SVM	%۸۵/۴۲	Core i5 650 system with 4GB memory	[۱۰۷]
CASME	SJ Wang ۲۰۱۴-	Discriminant Tensor Subspace Analysis (DTSA) and Extreme Learning Machine (ELM)		۴۷٪	استفاده از فقط ۶ ریز حالت	[۱۰۸]
SMIC	Huang, Xiaohua ۲۰۱۵-	LBP-TOP	SVM	%۵۷/۹۳	Temporal Interpolation Method (TIM) جهت نرمال کردن هر ویدیو به ۱۰ فریم	[۱۱۰]
SMIC, CASME	X Huang ۲۰۱۶-	SpatioTemporal Completed Local Quantization Patterns (STCLQP)		۷۵/۳۱٪	۶۸/۹۳ CASME=	[۱۱۱]
CASME	Zheng, Hao ۲۰۱۷-	2D Gabor filter	SVM	۷۱/۱۹٪	۶۴/۸۸ CASME II=	[۱۱۲]

Figure 3-14 Examples of micro-expressions and the related movement units from the CASME database [103]

3-8 Conclusion

In this chapter, the background research and activities conducted by others in the fields of the study were discussed. All the topics presented in this chapter serve as a background for the proposed methods in the next chapter. The databases used in this research were thoroughly presented along with their full specifications. Up-to-date methods in the fields of age estimation, gender recognition, and facial expression and micro-expression recognition were also discussed in detail.

Chapter 4 Proposed Methods

4-1 Introduction

This chapter provides a complete explanation of the proposed methods in this research. The main objective of this research is emotion recognition through facial expressions and micro-expressions using texture-depth images. However, additional findings will also be discussed, which are considered innovations in this research. These include age estimation, gender recognition, facial expression recognition, micro-expression recognition, a method for feature discovery and extraction from depth images, a combined method for feature extraction from texture images, a method for converting depth images into texture images such that spatial features from texture images can be applied to them, a method for facial detection and extraction from depth images, and a new database for facial expression, emotion, and micro-expression recognition. These all encompass the entire research.

4-2 Proposed Method for Expression and Micro-Expression Detection

Figure 4–1 shows the flowchart of the proposed method for facial expression and micro-expression recognition. Detailed explanations are visible within the flowchart. Additionally, Figure 4–2 visually presents a summary of this process. In this method, the database images are first read from the input. Then, various facial elements such as eyes, nose, and mouth are extracted from texture images using the Viola & Jones algorithm. Also, using the coordinates obtained from texture images and the proposed face detection and extraction method from depth images, facial elements are extracted from depth images. These depth elements are then converted into texture images using the proposed method (depth feature extraction). After applying the necessary preprocessing, a median filter is applied to the depth images, which enhances the stronger edges. To further highlight the remaining edges, the Unsharp Mask filter is used to sharpen them (the radius and amount parameters vary for each database). After resizing (depending on the image size of the database), the proposed filter is applied to texture images from 8 directions. In the next step, morphological post-processing (disk, line, and square shapes depending on the database needs) is applied to remove unnecessary points from the image. After

calculating the gradient of the images, spatial features such as LBP, HOG, LPQ, SURF, Gabor Filter, and HOGOM are extracted and applied to different facial regions in the texture image, and the features HOGOM and LPQ are applied to the extracted depth images. Dimension reduction or feature selection is performed using the Lasso method. Finally, $1 * n$ feature vectors are concatenated for texture and depth images to obtain the final $n * n$ feature matrix.

Figure 4-1 Flowchart of the proposed method for facial expression and micro-expression recognition.

Figure 4-2 The process of the proposed method for detecting facial expressions and micro-expressions visually.

Figure 4-3 The features extracted from the face using the V & J algorithm compared to three different datasets.

In Figure 4-3 samples of facial feature extraction from some of the datasets used by the V & J algorithm are displayed. The V & J algorithm is thoroughly explained in the previous chapter. To refer to this section, you can click on the link.

4-3 Proposed Method for Face Detection and Extraction from Depth Data

Figure 4-4 illustrates the flowchart of the proposed method for detecting and extracting the face from depth data. Figure 4-5 also visually represents this

process. The process begins by finding the smallest pixel value in the depth data that indicates the tip of the nose and the closest pixel to the sensor. After preprocessing the rectangular crop, a standard deviation filter is applied to define the head's elliptical shape. To extract the head's ellipse, an ellipse fitting method is used. The coordinates of the obtained ellipse are then applied to a copy of the image that has not had the standard deviation filter applied. The pixels inside the ellipse are selected, and the pixels outside the ellipse are replaced with either 0 or 255. Next, pixels with values ranging from 1 to 254, which represent the face image, are selected to remove extra sections. Finally, a percentage from all four edges of the image, including the chin, ears, hair, and the upper part of the forehead, is cropped. This value is considered $1/5$ of the image for both the right and left sides (ears), $1/7$ for the lower part of the image (chin), and $1/5$ for the upper part (hair and forehead).

Figure 4-4 The flowchart of the proposed facial detection method for depth images

Figure 4-5 The process of the proposed facial detection method from depth data

4-4 Proposed Method for Converting Depth Images to Texture (Depth Feature Extraction)

Figure 4-6 illustrates the flowchart of the proposed feature extraction method (converting depth to texture) from depth data. In this method, the first step is to detect and extract the face from depth data using the proposed facial detection method explained earlier or by using the method described in Figure 4-7. Next, a Gaussian filter with a sigma of 2 is applied to the image to smooth the model, which is necessary for the next step. At this stage, if the current pixel value is equal to the next and previous pixel values in both the horizontal and vertical directions, the current pixel is set to 1; otherwise, it is set to 255. A second Gaussian filter with a sigma of 2 is then applied to blur the obtained contours, preparing the image for texture description. At this point, since the depth image now closely resembles a texture image, texture image descriptors can be used for final feature extraction. Essentially, the proposed method eliminates the need for traditional depth feature extraction methods. In this stage, a combination of LBP+Haar+HOG features—known as the HOGOM method—is used, along with the LPQ method for blurred regions. As mentioned earlier, an alternative approach for facial detection and extraction from the

depth image can also be used. This approach considers only a percentage of pixels within a specific range that defines the facial region in the depth data. For instance, if the depth image values range from 1 to 255, then only values below 187 can be used to identify facial pixels. The threshold 187 is determined based on the sensor-to-sample distance in the proposed dataset and varies across different datasets depending on the sample-to-sensor distance.

Figure 4-6 The flowchart of the proposed feature extraction method for depth data

Figure 4-7 Summary of the Proposed Feature Extraction Method for Depth Data

Table 4 - 1 Proposed Edge Detection Filter

-۱.۲	-۰.۸	-۰.۶	.۲۱	۰.۸	۰.۶	-۰.۶	-۰.۸	-۰.۱	۰.۶	۰.۸	۰.۱
۰	۰	۰	۰	۰	۰	۰	۰	۰	۰	۰	۰
.۲۱	۰.۸	۰.۶	-۱.۲	-۰.۸	-۰.۶	۰.۶	۰.۸	۰.۱	-۰.۶	-۰.۸	-۰.۱
.۲۱	۰	-۱.۲	-۱.۲	۰	.۲۱	۰.۱	۰	-۰.۱	-۰.۱	۰	۰.۱
۰.۸	۰	-۰.۸	-۰.۸	۰	۰.۸	۰.۸	۰	-۰.۸	-۰.۸	۰	۰.۸
۰.۶	۰	-۰.۶	-۰.۶	۰	۰.۶	۰.۶	۰	-۰.۶	-۰.۶	۰	۰.۶

Figure 4-7 provides a top-down summary of the proposed feature extraction method for depth data (converting depth to texture). The extracted features are structured as vectors, which ultimately form a $1 * n$ vector per sample. If necessary, dimensionality reduction or feature selection (e.g., using the Lasso method) is applied to reduce the size of the extracted features. After extracting features from texture images, these vectors are merged with those obtained from depth-based texture representations. The resulting final feature matrix is then passed to the learning phase. After feature extraction and

dimensionality reduction from both depth and texture data, only a $1 * n$ vector per sample remains in the dataset, ready for the learning process.

4-5 Feature Combination

It is evident that each local feature of a digital image provides specific information. Information that is based on texture, appearance, edges and corners, brightness variations, smoothing and sharpening, etc. When performing object detection or recognition, there is no need to use complex algorithms, and for example, one of the texture-based methods such as LBP can be used for object recognition. However, when facing a phenomenon such as face recognition, where each object is different from another, it is necessary to extract more local and precise features. Combining these features may increase the computational time for feature extraction and training, but the final recognition accuracy increases significantly. Since the main objective of this research is to recognize facial expressions and micro-expressions, and each person's face is different from another, and the way emotions are expressed also varies from face to face, it is necessary to extract different local features and combine them. Additionally, the sampling conditions of the database in terms of type, size, and lighting levels should also be considered. Facial features are the muscle states of the face when expressing emotions, and these muscles differ greatly across ages, races, and genders. However, the underlying structure of all expressions in humans is the same, and by extracting good features, this structure can be discovered. The LBP (Local Binary Pattern) method is a powerful technique for texture analysis and is texture-based. LBP is a texture-based feature extraction method that has shown strong resistance to lighting variations. For this reason, it has been used in the proposed method to reduce the impact of different lighting conditions.

For face description, edge-based or appearance-based features can be used. Edge-based features consider the position, angle, or size of edge pixels. These features can be extracted from edge maps or image gradients. HOG (Histogram of Oriented Gradients) is a feature descriptor that can capture such characteristics. In the frequency domain, the image phase spectrum does not change significantly after smoothing, but the amplitude spectrum shows

noticeable variations. LPQ (Local Phase Quantization) is a local feature extracted from the phase spectrum in the frequency domain. It reduces the impact of blurring effects and can be useful for images affected by unwanted blurring. Additionally, using Gabor filters for face feature extraction is very common because they effectively extract facial wrinkles. Gabor filters, like LBP, are texture-based. However, both Gabor filters and LBP are sensitive to blurring, which reduces their classification accuracy when applied to blurred images. To overcome this, combining them with LPQ (which is robust against blurring, rotation, size changes, and brightness variations) is recommended. The SURF feature is also one of the features used for edge detection and blob detection.

SURF is a fast feature extraction method. Even when the image is rotated, it detects nearly the same feature points.

For example, combining HOG and SURF is effective for local shapes since it captures controlled edge structures while being robust to geometric transformations. Or, combining LBP and HOG is very useful when dealing with images with different lighting conditions and varying levels of detail. Additionally, the combination of HOG, Haar, and LBP is widely used due to its ability to handle various imaging conditions and its high efficiency, and this combination is known as HOGOM features. Our goal is to use six different features (LBP, Haar, LPQ, HOG, Gabor, and SURF) instead of just three, to account for all possible variations in imaging conditions. The characteristics and properties of each feature were discussed in the previous related works chapter, and their application method is explained in the following sections. However, raw images will not be directly used as input for these feature extraction methods. To further enhance the recognition accuracy, preprocessing steps are applied to remove all unnecessary image elements while preserving only the essential facial features. Figure 4–8 shows the application of five primary features on both texture and depth images from the Curtin Face database.

Figure 4-8 Visual results of applying five main features on two texture and depth images [71]

4-6 Local Binary Patterns (LBP)

Appearance features are essentially derived from color and texture, and these features are extracted from a local region of the image. The LBP feature [80] is considered a powerful method for texture analysis. This feature was introduced as a 3×3 square operator. LBP is a texture-based feature extraction method that has shown good resistance to changes in lighting conditions. For this reason, it has been used in the proposed method to minimize the effects of varying lighting conditions. To extract the texture feature of an image, a 3×3 neighborhood is considered for each pixel, and the value of that pixel is taken as the threshold. Then, for neighboring pixels with a value greater than or equal to the threshold, a value of one is assigned, while for smaller values, a value of zero is assigned.

Finally, the central pixel value is replaced with the weighted binary sum of its neighboring pixels, and the 3×3 window is shifted to the next pixel. The texture of the image is obtained by computing the histogram of these newly assigned pixel values. Figure 4-9 illustrates the operation of the LBP algorithm.

Figure 4-9 LBP algorithm operation (from left to right and top to bottom) [81]

4-7 Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG)

Edge-based or appearance-based features can be used to describe a face. In edge-based features, the location, angle, or size of the edge pixels are considered. Edge-based features can be extracted from the edge map or image gradient. Edge-based features at the region level contrast with those computed at the pixel level, as they are derived from local areas of the image. Compared to pixel-level features, these features adapt to some extent to local deformations of the face shape. Several methods have been proposed for computing region-level edge-based features. For example, edge features from a local region of an image can be obtained by approximating the edge pixel information within that region into discrete values and accumulating them into a histogram. A well-known example of this approach is the Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG).

This feature is computed from a rectangular (local) region of the image. Each edge pixel votes for a bin in the histogram designated for the edge direction. The

edge magnitude is used to weight the histogram bin. This method was initially designed for human detection and later used for facial component analysis. It captures local shape- and appearance-based features by utilizing the distribution of gradient intensity or edge orientations. The gradient magnitude at each pixel is accumulated into a histogram based on edge orientations. First, the image is divided into small regions from which the histogram of gradient orientations or edge directions is extracted. The collection of these histograms forms the HOG descriptor. After computing the image gradient, the edge orientations in the gradient image move from white to black. The stronger the contrast, the stronger the edge directions. These orientations range between 0–180 degrees or 0–360 degrees [82]. The image gradient in the horizontal and vertical directions can be easily obtained by applying the kernel in Figure 4–10 to the image or using traditional edge detection filters.

Figure 4–10 Gradient computation kernel in the HOG algorithm

Figure 4–11 Gradient direction movement from brighter areas to darker areas

Figure 4–12, from left to right, represents the magnitude and direction of the gradient for the texture and depth images. Additionally, the last image on the right illustrates the direction of the gradient arrows, which move from white to black pixels with a specific magnitude. Figure 4–13 also presents the magnitude and direction of the gradient for a portion of a color or texture image in a magnified view.

Figure 4-12 Image showing the magnitude, gradient direction, and also the orientations on the texture and depth images (from left to right)

Figure 4-13 Magnified view of the gradient magnitude and direction on a part of an image [83]

The arrows represent the edge directions, and the magnitude indicates the arrow length and the degree of difference. Finally, the histogram of each patch is computed and placed into different bins to complete the feature vector.

4-8 Local Phase Quantization (LPQ)

Local phase quantization (LPQ) is a local image feature in the frequency domain based on the phase value in the Fourier transform [84]. As evident in Figure 4-14, the effect of image blurring in the spatial domain has little impact on the phase spectrum in the frequency domain, whereas it completely alters the magnitude spectrum. Therefore, this feature and its interpretation can be used as an auxiliary feature in conditions of image blurring. Similarly, Figure 4-

15 demonstrates the same conditions for a depth image. The amount of change in the phase spectrum of the frequency domain after blurring or smoothing the image is close to zero.

Figure 4-14 The texture image in the frequency domain—the top row shows the original image, and the bottom row shows the result after applying the Gabor filter

Figure 4-15 The depth image in the frequency domain—the top row shows the original image, and the bottom row shows the result after applying the Gabor filter

The obtained angles can be directly converted into a feature vector, but this would result in a very long vector. Therefore, angles with moderate distortion are digitized through sampling. LPQ is based on calculating the short-time Fourier transform and is obtained locally on windows in the image [85].

Figure 4–16 The process of the LPQ algorithm (from left to right) [85]

In Figure 4–17, we observe the classification percentage for the methods LPQ, LBP, and Gabor Filter. As shown, as the power of the blurring filter increases (circular wavelet filter), the classification results of LBP and Gabor Filter decrease, while the result obtained from the LPQ algorithm does not change significantly.

Figure 4–17 The classification percentage for the methods LPQ, LBP, and Gabor Filter relative to changes in blur intensity [84]

In Figure 4–17, on the left, the standard deviation between 0-2 is applied to the image, and on the right, this standard deviation for the Gabor filter is considered between 0.5-1.5.

4-9 Gabor Filter

The Gabor filter, like LBP, is based on texture. Both the Gabor filter and LBP are sensitive to blurring, and blurred images reduce the classification accuracy for them. In various computer vision applications such as texture analysis and edge detection, Gabor functions are widely used. The Gabor filter is a linear and local filter. The convolution kernel of the Gabor filter is the product of a complex exponential function and a Gaussian. When the Gabor filters are properly and accurately tuned, they perform very well in detecting texture features and texture edges. Another feature of Gabor filters is their high joint frequency resolution. This means that their response is highly localized and tunable in both the spatial and frequency domains. This wavelet can be used as directional and scale-adaptive detectors for detecting lines and edges in images. Additionally, the statistical properties of this transform can be utilized to determine the structure and visual content of images. Gabor transform features have been applied in several image analysis applications, including texture classification, segmentation, image recognition, image registration, and motion tracking.

The LPQ calculation with short-term Fourier transform is the same as the Gabor filter. For instance, in Figure 4–21, a Gabor filter with a wavelength of 8 is used at directions 0, 22, 45, 67, 90, 112, 135, and 180 degrees. The Gabor filter is a type of band-pass filter, meaning it passes certain frequency bands while stopping the others. This filter gives the highest response to regions where sudden texture changes occur. Essentially, the two-dimensional Gabor filter is modeled (multiplied) by a sinusoidal plane wave. The most important feature of the Gabor filter is its resistance to changes in brightness, rotation, and scaling.

Complex

$$g(x, y; \lambda, \theta, \psi, \sigma, \gamma) = \exp\left(-\frac{x'^2 + \gamma^2 y'^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \exp\left(i\left(2\pi\frac{x'}{\lambda} + \psi\right)\right)$$

Real

$$g(x, y; \lambda, \theta, \psi, \sigma, \gamma) = \exp\left(-\frac{x'^2 + \gamma^2 y'^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \cos\left(2\pi\frac{x'}{\lambda} + \psi\right)$$

Imaginary

$$g(x, y; \lambda, \theta, \psi, \sigma, \gamma) = \exp\left(-\frac{x'^2 + \gamma^2 y'^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \sin\left(2\pi\frac{x'}{\lambda} + \psi\right)$$

where

$$x' = x \cos \theta + y \sin \theta$$

and

$$y' = -x \sin \theta + y \cos \theta$$

Figure 4–18 The relationships of the Gabor filter (real and imaginary parts)

- σ : The standard deviation used in the Gaussian function applied in the Gabor filter, which alters the width of the variations in the waveform.
- θ : The angle of the wavelets—this is the most important parameter and determines which features of the image the filter responds to.
- λ : The size of the sinusoidal wavelength.
- γ : The spatial domain ratio—determines the ellipticity of the wavelet, with a value of 1 indicating that the Gaussian function is circular.
- ψ : The phase shift.

In Figure 4–19, we observe the Gabor filter with various frequencies and directions in both 2D and 3D forms.

Figure 4–19 The Gabor filter with different frequencies and directions in both 2D and 3D forms [86]

In Figure 4–20, from left to right, we see the sinusoidal model with a 30-degree angle on the X-axis, the Gaussian kernel, and finally the Gabor filter, which is the result of multiplying the previous two models together.

Figure 4–20 (From left to right) the sinusoidal model with a 30-degree angle on the X-axis, the Gaussian kernel, and finally the Gabor filter

Figure 4–21 The Gabor filter with a wavelength of 8 and at angles of 0, 22, 45, 67, 90, 112, 135, and 180 degrees

4-10 Haar Feature

This method is typically used for object detection and was introduced by Mr. Viola in 2001. It uses a large number of positive and negative cube-like images, or True-False images, for detection. Positive images contain the object of interest, while negative images contain objects used for training the classifier [88]. In Figure 4–22, the set of pixel values within the black rectangle is subtracted from the set of values within the white rectangle. These rectangles represent features, and in Figure 4–22, we can see several types of features used, from left to right.

Figure 4–22 Types of feature cubes in the Haar method [88]

The calculation of rectangular features from the image integral is obtained using Figure 4–23.

$$ii(x, y) = \sum_{x' \leq x, y' \leq y} i(x', y')$$

$$s(x, y) = s(x, y - 1) + i(x, y)$$

$$ii(x, y) = ii(x - 1, y) + s(x, y)$$

Figure 4–23 The relationship for calculating rectangular features from the image integral

Where x, y represent the pixel values of the rectangles, and $ii(x, y)$ is the integral image, and $i(x, y)$ is the original image. $S(x, y)$ is the accumulated sum. The integral image facilitates the summation of pixel values, where each pixel in the integral image is the sum of its current pixel value plus the values of the pixel above it and to the left. [89] This means that the value of each pixel in the image is the sum of its previous pixel values. For example, in Figure 4–24, the value of

the cell at row 5 and column 5 in the original image has the highest value for the integral image.

Figure 4–24 The original image (on the left) and the integral image (on the right) [89]

$$\text{startingRow} = \text{sR} = 1$$

$$\text{startingColumn} = \text{sC} = 3$$

$$\text{endingRow} = \text{eR} = 2$$

$$\text{endingColumn} = \text{eC} = 4$$

The integral sum of the region = integral image (eR+1, eC+1) - integral image (eR+1, sC) - integral image (sR, eC+1) + integral image (sR, sC)

$$\text{integral sum of the region} = 99 - 69 - 0 + 0 = 30$$

Figure 4–25 How to calculate the integral image (second figure)

Using the integral image allows the sum of pixels within a rectangle of any size to be obtained with only three additions. The integral image is useful when the result of convolving an image with box filters needs to be calculated. Box filters are filters that can be divided into rectangles with a constant weight. Thus, during convolution with the image, only the sum of pixels in the rectangular regions needs to be calculated and multiplied by the corresponding weight. After obtaining the corresponding integral image from the original image, the integral image helps calculate the sum of any rectangle with only three addition operations, making the convolution process much faster than the usual method.

In Figure 4–26, two simple rectangular features are used to detect the eyes. It is evident that the eye area is darker than the nose area due to the indentation and is located between the two eyes. Therefore, by using a simple rectangular feature and calculating the difference between the pixel values of two rectangles, the eye region can be detected.

Figure 4–26 Using Haar features for eye detection

By applying numerous positive and negative rectangles on the face, its features can be extracted. Ultimately, using well-known descriptors, these regions can be represented as feature vectors.

Additionally, by converting the 2D image matrix into a vector, we can extract features from the image vector as follows. This method is in the signal processing domain and is known as the Haar Wavelet Transform (HWT).

- $w = [1/\sqrt{2} \ -1/\sqrt{2}]$; %haar wavelet function
- $d = \text{length}(f)$;
- $m = 1:d/2$;
- $d1 = f(2*m-1).*w(1) + f(2*m).*w(2)$; % haar wavelet transform

Where w is the Haar wavelet function, f is the signal, d is the length of the signal, and $d1$ is the Haar wavelet transform for the desired signal.

4-11 Speeded Up Robust Features (SURF)

This method is both a feature detection and description technique. It has a high processing speed and can detect nearly the same feature points even if the image is rotated.

1. First, the integral image is calculated, similar to the Haar method, to increase computation speed.
2. Then, feature points are detected using the Hessian algorithm [90].
3. Scale-space is constructed.
4. Extremum points (maximum points) are determined.
5. Feature vectors are generated.

Note: The SURF algorithm is essentially an advanced version of the SIFT algorithm [91], but it is 3 to 5 times faster than SIFT due to the integral image calculation. Additionally, the final matrix in SURF has dimensions of 64, while in SIFT, it is 128. However, this does not result in any loss of accuracy. The SIFT algorithm is essentially the same as SURF but without step 1 mentioned above [92].

In the SURF algorithm, due to the high accuracy and efficiency of the Hessian matrix, the detector is based on the Hessian matrix. The goal is to detect blob-like structures in locations where the determinant of the Hessian matrix is maximized. In Figure 4–27, the second derivative of the image is computed along the x and y axes; each axis individually detects only edges. However, the intersection of these axes, using the filters in Figure 4–28, detects corners, which contain more information. These filters are applied simply through convolution on the image. The difference between these filters and Gaussian filters is their high execution speed, as only part of the image kernel has weight, unlike Gaussian kernels, where different weights exist throughout the entire kernel.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial I^2}{\partial x^2} & \frac{\partial I^2}{\partial x \partial y} \\ \frac{\partial I^2}{\partial y \partial x} & \frac{\partial I^2}{\partial y^2} \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 4–27 The equation for the second derivative of the image

Figure 4–28 Detector filters

The determinant is calculated using equation 3-41.

$$\det(H_{approx}) = D_{xx} D_{yy} - (\omega D_{xy})^2$$

Figure 4–29 Calculation of the image determinant

ω is a number between 0 and 1 used to balance the determinant of the Hessian matrix.

In the third step, the images are first divided into different categories, usually up to five. Then, for each category, a fixed number of images is processed at various sizes or scales. Finally, a Gaussian blur filter with different sigma values is applied to each category's images.

In the next step, the difference between images in each category is calculated to reduce the total number of images. Since this difference operation is applied to progressively blurred images, the resulting difference image highlights edge features.

At each stage of the difference operation, an image that has both a previous and next image is selected. For each pixel in the current image, its intensity is compared with the corresponding pixels in the previous and next images within the same category. If a 3×3 kernel is used, the total number of compared pixels is 26. If the target pixel is either greater or smaller than all 26 surrounding pixels, it is selected as a candidate pixel. This candidate pixel is referred to as an extremum point.

Figure 4–30 SURF Algorithm (Part One)

Equation from Figure 4–31 is used to compute and apply the Gaussian filter with different sigma values on the candidate image.

$$L(x, y, \sigma) = G(x, y, \sigma) * I(x, y)$$

$$G(x, y, \sigma) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma^2} e^{-\frac{x^2+y^2}{2\sigma^2}}$$

Figure 4–31 Equation for applying the Gaussian filter to the image

Figure 4–32 SURF Algorithm (Part Two)

Figure 4–33 SURF Algorithm (Part Three)

Figure 4–34 SURF Algorithm (Part Four)

Figure 4–35 Using Haar features to determine feature orientations

Figure 4–36 The movement of feature orientations along the extremum points

After finding the corner points in step 2 and the extremum points in step 4, the next step is to form the feature vector, which, like the SIFT method, is based

on the distribution of intensity values of the neighboring pixels around the extremum points, in the direction of the greatest changes.

4-12 Feature Selection Using Lasso Method

When the dimensions of the feature matrix (in terms of the number of features, not the number of observations) are high, there is a need to remove less effective features in the learning process.

This feature reduction is done for various reasons, such as reducing computational load, selecting a fixed number of the best features, and eliminating features that increase error. There are various methods for this purpose. Some of these methods include PCA [95], Regression [96][97], and the Lasso method [96][97], which we use in this research. Lasso, introduced by Tibshirani in 1996, is an improved version of the Regression method. PCA reduces data to smaller dimensions by projecting the original data onto a unit basis, while the Regression method reduces dimensions by hierarchically increasing and decreasing dimensions until no further improvement is seen. However, the Lasso method works by eliminating redundant features through reducing the weights of features towards zero. This method is much faster and more accurate than the previous methods, but when the number of features exceeds the number of observations, it ultimately selects the number of features equal to the number of observations. The Regression method is computationally complex but simple to implement and understand. In Regression, we look for coefficients that minimize the sum of squared errors (SSE) between predicted and actual values. Image 4-37 shows how to calculate the SSE or sum of squared errors.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2$$

Figure 4–37 The formula for the sum of squared errors

However, regularization methods are added to the regression model to prevent overfitting. Overfitting occurs when the number of features is much

larger than the number of observations or samples, and the data becomes highly tangled or entangled. In such situations, Lasso Regularization is used to select features. Figure 4–38 illustrates the overfitting model (green line) and the regularized model (black line).

Figure 4–38 Overfitting model (green) and regularized model (black) [98]

The fuzzy Lasso method addresses the issue of the regression method by adding several functions of the existing coefficients to the model. The regression method only generates one set of regression coefficients, whereas the Lasso method produces a minimum of 100 or more sets of regression coefficients, depending on the value of lambda. This means that, in addition to finding coefficients that minimize the sum of squared errors between the predicted and actual values, several functions of these coefficients are added to the model. Figure 4–39 illustrates the calculation of Lasso regularization, where lambda is the regularization weight related to the second part of the equation.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 + \lambda \sum_{j=1}^p |\beta_j|$$

Figure 4–39 Lasso regularization formula

N is the number of observations. y_i is the predicted value, and $y^{\wedge}i$ is the actual value of the model. The model coefficients are stored in β , and p is the number of β coefficients in each model. When the λ value increases, the number of non-zero elements in β decreases.

Thus, the Lasso regularization method reduces the absolute values of the regression coefficients. Initially, Lasso starts with a low λ value and increases it during successive iterations, pushing the coefficient values toward zero. Any feature whose corresponding coefficient becomes zero is removed from the equation, leading to dimension or feature reduction. But how do we choose between these models? The answer lies in the Lasso plot. After applying the Lasso method on the feature matrix, we end up with a graph like the one in Figure 4–40.

The relationship between λ variations and mean squared error is displayed in this figure. Each red dot represents the mean squared error for the current model. Each vertical line over the red points shows the error range for the current model. The green circle on the right indicates the λ value that minimizes the mean squared error, while the blue circle on the left indicates the λ value with the maximum shrinkage and a certain standard deviation. It is recommended to choose a value for λ between these two circles for the final model.

Figure 4–40 The output of the Lasso feature selection method on the feature matrix of the JAFFE database

4-13 Iranian Kinect Face Database (IKFDB)

To address the issues present in many available facial recognition and expression databases collected using depth sensors and to create the first Iranian facial depth database, a comprehensive and high-quality database was developed to overcome many of these challenges. This database was collected using the Kinect v2 sensor with a resolution of 1080×1920 for texture data and 424×512 for depth data. It serves three main purposes: face recognition, facial expression and emotion recognition, and micro-expression detection. This database is one of the few available for micro-expression recognition. Similar databases suffer from issues such as inconsistent lighting conditions, sensor displacement in terms of height and distance from the face, unsuitable backgrounds, weak or sometimes incorrect facial expressions, improper depth data collection due to incorrect sensor-to-face distance, and lack of age diversity. These problems have been addressed as much as possible in the proposed database. Approximately 70% of the database was collected at the Elahiyeh Language Institute in Rudehen, Damavand County, Tehran Province, while the remaining data was recorded in various locations over two weeks. A vacant classroom was converted into a data collection environment, and after the students' classes ended, they were invited to participate in the data collection process as database subjects. The recording process for each sample or model took approximately 15 to 20 minutes. The total number of samples in the database is 40 individuals (16 females and 24 males), with an age range of 7 to 70 years. Each facial expression was recorded in 150 video frames, resulting in a final database size of 10.8 GB for both texture and depth data. The database includes seven primary facial expressions: neutral, happiness, anger, surprise, sadness, disgust, and fear. It also accounts for 90-degree head rotations along horizontal and vertical axes to support face recognition. To capture micro-expressions, participants were instructed to gradually transition from the lowest to the highest intensity of each facial expression within a specified timeframe. Additionally, a consent form was signed by both parties in two copies to prevent any misuse. The terms of the agreement are as follows:

- The personal information of individuals included in the database remains confidential, and the responsibility for protecting this data lies with the database administrator.
- The database content is only accessible through the university and is provided to the relevant student under the supervision of the department head or academic advisor, who bears responsibility for its use.
- The participants or models in the database do not hold any ownership rights over the database.
- The database is intended solely for scientific purposes and will not be used for commercial applications.

The database was named the "Iranian Kinect Face Database (IKFDB)". Figure 4–41 illustrates the data collection environment using the Kinect v2 sensor.

Figure 4–41 Environment and Method of Collecting and Creating the IKFDB Database

In Figure 4–42, several samples from the database are displayed in different facial expressions, presented in both texture and depth data formats. Figure 4–43 illustrates four micro-expressions—anger, disgust, surprise, and happiness—using both texture and depth data for four different individuals from the database. The key regions influencing the appearance of micro-expressions have been highlighted using rectangles. Additionally, head rotation data is utilized to improve facial recognition accuracy.

Figure 4–42 Applying Primary Facial Expressions and Head Rotation for Different Samples of the Proposed Database (Texture and Depth Data)

Figure 4–43 Applying Four Micro Facial Expressions from Samples of the Proposed Database (Texture and Depth Data)

4-14 Proposed Age Estimation Method

Figure 4–44 illustrates the flowchart of the proposed method for age estimation. In this flowchart, images are first retrieved from the database, and after face detection and necessary preprocessing, the proposed edge detection filter is applied to the image. The pixel density is then calculated and normalized between the ages of the youngest and oldest individuals in the database. For depth data, the same process is followed, except that instead of applying the proposed filter, the image entropy is calculated. Figure 4–45 visually summarizes the steps of the proposed age estimation method.

Figure 4-44 Flowchart of the Proposed Age Estimation Method

Figure 4-45 Visual Representation of the Summary of the Proposed Age Estimation Method

4-15 Image Entropy

Image entropy represents the average information obtained from a number n of observations. Entropy expresses the disorder (chaos) or uncertainty of a system. Explaining exactly what entropy is can be quite challenging. Understanding the concept of entropy is at least more complex than understanding and explaining physical concepts such as energy, force, momentum, and velocity. This is because entropy is not tangible and is often defined as a measure of disorder. However, in image processing, entropy effectively helps in edge detection for depth images. The fundamental concepts and theoretical basis of entropy were introduced by Claude Shannon in 1948 [2] [93].

$$H(\mathbf{z}) = -\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} P_i \log P_i$$

Figure 4-46 Entropy equation

where N represents the number of gray levels, and P_i is the probability associated with the gray level in question. The higher the entropy value, the more complex the image is. Entropy essentially calculates the complexity of the pixels surrounding the target pixel, which is provided through a structural

element or kernel. It also detects the local distribution of gray levels that are imperceptible. The equation in Figure 4–46 illustrates how linear entropy is calculated. Figure 4–47 shows a simple example of solving the entropy problem for a few samples. Furthermore, Figure 4–48 presents an example of image entropy with various structural elements for a number of depth images. The first row displays depth images, the second row shows image entropy with a disk-shaped structural element of radius 4, the third row shows image entropy with a linear structural element of length 8 at a 180-degree angle, and the fourth row displays image entropy with a square-shaped structural element of size 9 * 9 matrix.

Symbol a_i	Probability p_i	Information (in bits) $I(a_i) = -\log p_i$
0	1/2	1
1	1/4	2
2	1/8	3
3	1/16	4
4	1/32	5
5	1/64	6
6	1/64	6

$$H(z) = -\sum_{i=0}^6 p_i \log p_i = -[1/2 \log 1/2 + 1/4 \log 1/4 + \dots + 1/64 \log 1/64]$$

$$= [1/2 + 1/2 + \dots + 3/32] = 63/32 = 1.96875 \text{ bits}$$

Figure 4–47 A simple example of solving the entropy problem

Figure 4–48 Entropy of an image for several depth images with different structural elements

4-16 Conclusion

When a feature or another dimension, such as depth, is involved, naturally, analytical methods are required; however, similarities exist between depth data and texture data. If depth data can be structurally mapped to texture data, then texture data analysis methods can be directly applied to the transformed depth data. Therefore, a method was considered for this transformation. By selecting index pixels in the depth image, it became possible to convert depth data into a texture-like data, on which texture feature extraction algorithms can be directly applied. In this chapter, a new method for age estimation based on the pixel density of the region around the nose was proposed, which due to its suitable speed, could be useful for real-time applications. Additionally, a new method for extracting faces from depth data was introduced and examined, which performs well compared to other methods. A combined method was also presented by integrating 6 spatial features of texture data, which, with the help of suitable preprocessing, can overcome diverse image data conditions. In facial expression and micro-expression detection, facial elements were separated using image processing techniques, and then spatial features related to each were applied to the respective images. A database for detecting facial expressions and micro-expressions was also provided, addressing the issues present in existing databases.

Chapter 5 Evaluation and Results

5-1 Introduction

In this chapter, the evaluation of the proposed methods and those presented in the previous chapter will be discussed. For this purpose, tools and materials will be used, which are explained below. These evaluations will be conducted for all proposed methods and the valid and new databases in this field. A detailed explanation of the databases is provided in the literature review chapter, and in this chapter, they are presented in the form of a table. The evaluation will be based on training and test data for each database. Specifically, 70% of the data in each database will be used for supervised training, and the remaining 30% will be used without labels for testing the system. Some of the results show improvements compared to previous works in the relevant field, while others are being tested for the first time.

5-2 Evaluation Tools and Materials

The algorithms and methods used to test the strength of the system or the proposed method in the research are called the system evaluation tools and materials.

- Support Vector Machine [99]
- Multilayer Neural Networks [101] [100]
- Evaluation Databases

5-2-1 Evaluation Databases

Table 3- 1 shows the characteristics of the texture databases used in the research. Table 3-2 displays the characteristics of the depth texture databases used in the research. The complete specifications of the texture databases for facial micro-expressions are also provided in Table 3- 4.

5-3 Results from Proposed Methods

In the previous chapter, the proposed age estimation method was explained. Figure 5.1 presents the results of this method applied to the entire sample of the Curtin Face DB and IKFDB databases. In these bar plots, the horizontal axis represents the samples or individuals from the database, while the vertical axis shows the age of the sample. To calculate the difference between the age label

and the obtained value, the mean absolute error factor was used [113]. The colors seen in Table 5 - 1 indicate: red: improvement over the results of other researchers, blue: results that were performed for the first time on that database, purple: results that were performed for the first time on the proposed database, and green: results that have never been done on any texture-depth database before, which is the facial micro-expression detection task.

Table 5 - 1 The results obtained from the proposed methods

پایگاه داده	استفاده در	نوع پایگاه داده	فقط بافت	فقط عمق	مجموع آموزشی	مجموع آزمایشی
JAFFE	تشخیص حالات چهره	RGB	SVM=97.50%	-	97.50%	96.71%
			MLNN=97.88%	-	97.88%	97.3%
KDEF	تشخیص جنسیت	RGB	SVM=99.8%	-	99.8%	100%
			MLNN=100%	-	100%	100%
EURECOM	تشخیص جنسیت	RGB-D	SVM=93.12%	89.28%	94.19%	93.29%
	تشخیص حالات چهره		MLNN=95.61%	92.33%	96.82%	97%
Curtin Face	تخمین سن	RGB-D	SVM=96.60%	91.28%	97.40%	97.59%
			MLNN=98.47%	95.50%	98.66%	99%
VAP RGBD	تشخیص حالات چهره	RGB-D	MAE= 12.67	MAE= 16.09	MAE= 11.48	
			-	-	-	-
VAP RGB-D-T	تشخیص حالات چهره	RGB-D-T	SVM=96%	89.50%	97.92%	98.14%
			MLNN=99.23%	93.86%	99.80%	98.01%
FEEDB	تشخیص جنسیت	RGB-D	SVM=93.99%	عمق	95.97%	95.80%
			MLNN=96.80%	86.60%	96.11%	97.59%
Face Grabber	تشخیص حالات چهره	RGB-D	88.75%	گرمایی		
	تشخیص ریز حالات چهره		94.34%	95.73%		
CASME	تشخیص ریز حالات چهره	RGB	SVM=85.19%	74.50%	89.15%	87.15%
			MLNN=89%	80.30%	90.10%	91.11%
IKFDB	تشخیص حالات چهره	RGB-D	SVM=92.58%	88.08%	93.60%	93.17%
	تشخیص ریز حالات چهره		MLNN=92%	90.90%	95.19%	94.91%
IKFDB	تشخیص ریز حالات چهره	RGB	SVM=68.39%	65.15%	73.18%	75%
	تشخیص حالات چهره		MLNN=71.20%	70%	74.09%	80.21%
IKFDB	تشخیص ریز حالات چهره	RGB	SVM= 69.83%	-	SVM=	70.37%
	تشخیص حالات چهره		MLNN=72.09	-	69.83%	71.76%
IKFDB	تخمین سن	RGB-D	MAE= 14.88	MAE= 20.75	MAE= 13.03	
	تشخیص جنسیت		-	-	-	-
IKFDB	تشخیص حالات چهره	RGB-D	SVM=96.60%	91.51%	97%	97.28%
	تشخیص ریز حالات چهره		MLNN=98.63%	92%	99.12%	97.16%
IKFDB	تشخیص ریز حالات چهره	RGB-D	SVM=95.90	94.75%	96.19%	95.85%
	تشخیص حالات چهره		MLNN=97%	94.90%	98.03%	98.18%
IKFDB	تشخیص ریز حالات چهره	RGB-D	SVM=76.87%	73.46%	78.90%	82.47%
	تشخیص حالات چهره		MLNN=80.09%	76.56%	84.13%	85.40%

Figure 5–1 The bar plot of the proposed age estimation method on samples from two databases (Curtin Face DB, IKFDB)

Table 5 - 1 presents the results obtained from the proposed methods, including gender detection, age estimation, facial expression recognition, and micro-expression detection, across 10 different databases, including texture-only databases and texture-depth databases collected using different sensors. Additionally, the results of the proposed methods on the proposed database are presented in the last five rows. In this table, from left to right, the database, its application in this study, the type of images in the database in terms of texture and depth, the recognition accuracy of texture training data using SVM and MLNN classifiers, the recognition accuracy of depth training data using the mentioned classifiers, the recognition accuracy for both texture and depth data using the mentioned classifiers, and finally, the recognition accuracy for test data in terms of texture and depth data using the mentioned classifiers are shown.

Table 5 - 2 and Table 5 - 4 show the results obtained from applying the proposed method for facial expression recognition on 6 texture-only and texture-depth databases, classified by SVM and MLNN classifiers, respectively. Table 5 - 3 and Table 5 - 5 display the results obtained from the proposed method for micro-expression detection on 3 databases. These tables show the classification accuracy for each facial expression and micro-expression class. The

results are displayed based on factors such as true positive rate, false negative rate, correct observations, and incorrect observations for each class and the entire classes, in the form of a confusion matrix. As observed, the results using the MLNN classifier show better performance compared to the SVM classifier.

Table 5 - 2 The results of the proposed method for facial expression recognition on 6 databases using the SVM classifier

پایگاه داده	خنتی	خوشحالی	عصبانیت	غم	تعجب	انزجار	ترس	مجموع آموزشی	مجموع آزمایشی
JAFFE	100%	97%	94%	98%	99%	99%	96%	97.50%	96.71%
EURECOM	97%	97%	-	-	98%	-	-	97.40%	97.59%
VAP RGB-D	96%	98%	97%	99%	99%	-	-	97.92%	98.14%
VAP RGB-D-T	94%	94%	99%	-	97%	-	-	95.97%	95.80%
Face Grabber	92%	95%	90%	89%	96%	96%	94%	93.60%	93.17%
IKFDB	95%	98%	96%	96%	99%	97%	97%	96.19%	95.85%

Table 5 - 3 The results of the proposed method for micro-expression recognition on 3 databases using the SVM classifier

پایگاه داده	خنتی	خوشحالی	عصبانیت	غم	تعجب	انزجار	ترس	مجموع آموزشی	مجموع آزمایشی
Face Grabber	69%	78%	76%	73%	75%	72%	72%	73.18%	75%
IKFDB	79%	77%	74%	78%	81%	78%	80%	78.90%	82.47%
CASME	74%	65%	72%	68%	69%	70%	70%	69.83%	70.37%

Table 5 - 4 The results of the proposed method for facial expression recognition on 6 databases using the MLNN classifier

پایگاه داده	خنتی	خوشحالی	عصبانیت	غم	تعجب	انزجار	ترس	مجموع آموزشی	مجموع آزمایشی
JAFFE	99%	99%	96%	98%	98%	99%	97%	97.88%	97.3%
EURECOM	98%	98%	-	-	100%	-	-	98.66%	99%
VAP RGB-D	99%	98%	99%	100%	100%	-	-	99.80%	98.01%
VAP RGB-D-T	94%	95%	100%	-	97%	-	-	96.11%	97.59%
Face Grabber	91%	96%	96%	95%	95%	93%	96%	95.19%	94.91%
IKFDB	96%	99%	97%	96%	100%	99%	98%	98.03%	98.18%

Table 5 - 5 The results of the proposed method for micro facial expression recognition on 3 databases using the MLNN classifier

پایگاه داده	خنتی	خوشحالی	عصبانیت	غم	تعجب	انزجار	ترس	مجموع آموزشی	مجموع آزمایشی
Face Grabber	74%	78%	73%	72%	78%	77%	69%	74.09%	80.21%
IKFDB	80%	88%	83%	83%	86%	85%	83%	84.13%	85.40%
CASME	81%	69%	70%	69%	69%	71%	75%	72.09	71.76%

The results of the proposed method for facial expression recognition and micro-expression recognition on the IKFDB database using the SVM classifier are presented in Table 5 - 6 and Table 5 - 7. As observed, the proposed method performs well on the suggested database, achieving an accuracy of 96.19% in the test phase and 95.85% in the training phase for facial expression recognition. Additionally, for micro-expression recognition, the method achieved an accuracy of 78.90% in the training phase and 82.47% in the test phase, which is relatively acceptable. However, the results obtained using the MLNN classifier were somewhat better, with 98.03% and 98.18% accuracy for the training and test data for facial expression recognition. The MLNN classifier also outperformed the SVM classifier for micro-expression recognition, achieving an accuracy of 84.13% for the training data and 85.40% for the test data. The sample size selected from this database consisted of 4000 images (2000 texture images and 2000 depth images), with 571 texture and depth images per class (285 texture and 285 depth images). The images selected contained the most expressive facial states and those with moderate intensity expressions, while images with weaker expressions (less than 0.5 seconds) were chosen for the micro-expression recognition phase.

Table 5 - 6 The confusion matrix of the training data for facial expression recognition, IKFDB database with the SVM classifier

خوشحالی	542	95%	-	-	18	3%	5	1%	5	1%	-
خوشحالی	-	-	559	98%	-	-	11	2%	-	-	-
عصبانیت	11	2%	-	-	549	96%	-	-	11	2%	-
غم	22	4%	-	-	-	-	549	96%	-	-	-
تعجب	-	-	5	1%	-	-	-	-	566	99%	-
انزجار	-	-	-	-	11	2%	-	-	55	97%	5
ترس	-	-	-	-	-	-	5	1%	11	2%	55
-	خوشحالی	خوشحالی	عصبانیت	غم	تعجب	انزجار	ترس				
	542	95%	28	5%	571						
	559	98%	11	2%	571						
	549	96%	22	4%	571						
	549	96%	22	4%	571						
	566	99%	5	1%	571						
	554	97%	16	3%	571						
	554	97%	16	3%	571						
مشاهده صحیح		مشاهده غلط		مشاهدات							

	نرخ مثبت صحیح		نرخ منفی غلط	4000
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Table 5 - 7 The confusion matrix of the training data for micro facial expression recognition, IKFDB database with the SVM classifier

خنتی	451	79%	28	5%	40	7%	18	3%	-	34	6%	-
خوشحالی	45	8%	440	77%	18	3%	-	45	8%	-	23	4%
عصبانیت	34	6%	11	2%	422	74%	51	9%	18	3%	11	2%
غم	23	4%	5	1%	58	10%	445	78%	28	5%	-	11
تعجب	5	1%	40	7%	18	3%	5	1%	462	81%	-	40
انزجار	23	4%	18	3%	23	4%	18	3%	5	1%	44	78%
ترس	-	-	28	5%	23	4%	18	3%	23	4%	23	4%
-	خنتی	خوشحالی	عصبانیت	غم	تعجب	انزجار	ترس					
	451	79%	120	21%	571							
	440	77%	131	23%	571							
	422	74%	148	26%	571							
	445	78%	125	22%	571							
	462	81%	108	19%	571							
	445	78%	127	22%	571							
	456	80%	115	20%	571							
مشاهده صحیح	نرخ مثبت صحیح	مشاهده غلط	نرخ منفی غلط	مشاهدات								
				4000								

Table 5 - 8 and Table 5 - 9 display the results of the proposed method on the Face Grabber database for facial expression and micro-expression recognition, using the SVM classifier. Due to the novelty of this dataset, facial and micro-expression recognition has been performed for the first time on this dataset by this research. The proposed method performed better on facial expressions than on micro-expressions on this dataset, just as it did on the proposed dataset. The results indicate that in the facial expression recognition section, during both the training and testing phases, the accuracy was 93.60% and 93.17%, respectively. However, in the micro-expression section, the accuracy achieved was 73.18% in training and 85% in testing. The results obtained for this dataset using the MLNN classifier were better than those with the SVM classifier, with recognition accuracy of 94.91% and 80.21% for the training data. Additionally, the number of selected samples for separate facial and micro-expression

recognition was 5000 images (2500 texture images and 2500 depth images), with the facial expression intensity level similar to the IKFDB dataset. The 11.91% improvement in the proposed method's results over the results obtained by Mr. Sen Yuan in 2017 [79] indicates the effectiveness of the proposed method on this dataset. Moreover, the recognition of micro-expressions has been performed for the first time on this dataset.

Table 5 - 8 The confusion matrix for the training data of facial expression recognition, using the Face Grabber database with the SVM classifier

خنثی	656	92%	-	-	58	8%	-	-	-	-	-	-
خوشحالی	21	3%	678	95%	-	-	14	2%	-	-	-	-
عصبانیت	36	5%	-	643	90%	-	-	-	36	5%	-	-
غم	36	5%	-	-	636	89%	-	-	14	2%	29	4%
تعجب	-	-	29	4%	-	-	685	96%	-	-	-	-
انزجار	-	-	-	14	2%	-	-	-	685	96%	14	2%
ترس	-	-	-	7	1%	-	-	-	36	5%	671	94%
-	خنثی	خوشحالی	عصبانیت	غم	تعجب	انزجار	ترس					
	656	92%	58	8%	714							
	678	95%	35	95%	714							
	643	90%	72	10%	714							
	636	89%	79	11%	714							
	685	96%	29	4%	714							
	685	96%	28	4%	714							
	671	94%	43	6%	714							
	مشاهده صحیح	نرخ مثبت صحیح	مشاهده غلط	نرخ منفی غلط	مشاهدات							
					5000							

Table 5 - 9 The confusion matrix for the training data of micro-expression recognition, using the Face Grabber database with the SVM classifier

خنثی	450	69%	142	20%	-	-	21	3%	14	2%	42	6%	
خوشحالی	107	15%	557	78%	-	-	28	4%	-	-	21	3%	
عصبانیت	78	11%	-	543	76%	50	7%	-	42	6%	-	-	
غم	50	7%	-	-	12%	521	73%	-	36	5%	21	3%	
تعجب	57	8%	114	16%	-	-	536	75%	-	-	7	1%	
انزجار	93	13%	36	5%	50	7%	-	21	3%	51	72%	-	
ترس	36	5%	28	4%	21	3%	14	2%	-	78	11%	51	72%
-	خنثی	خوشحالی	عصبانیت	غم	تعجب	انزجار	ترس						
	450	69%	264	31%	714								
	557	78%	157	22%	714								

543	76%	171	24%	714
521	73%	193	27%	714
536	75%	178	25%	714
514	72%	200	28%	714
514	72%	200	25%	714
مشاهده صحیح	نرخ مثبت صحیح	مشاهده غلط	نرخ منفی غلط	مشاهدات
				5000

Table 5 - 10 The confusion matrix for the training data of micro-expression recognition, using the CASME database with the MLNN classifier

خنثی	173	81%	15	7%	2	1%	22	10%	-	-	2	1%		
خوشحالی	11	5%	147	69%	-	-	2	1%	31	15%	21	10%	2	1%
عصبانیت	7	3%	2	1%	149	70%	37	17%	-	-	15	7%	4	2%
غم	14	6%	4	2%	41	19%	147	69%	4	2%	4	2%	-	-
تعجب	24	11%	31	15%	-	-	-	-	147	69%	7	3%	4	2%
انزجار	2	1%	19	9%	15	7%	10	5%	2	1%	152	71%	14	6%
ترس	9	4%	7	3%	9	4%	-	-	10	5%	19	9%	16	75%
-	خنثی	خوشحالی	عصبانیت	غم	تعجب	انزجار	ترس							
	173	81%	41	19%	214									
	147	69%	67	31%	214									
	149	70%	65	30%	214									
	147	69%	67	31%	214									
	147	69%	67	31%	214									
	152	71%	62	29%	214									
	160	75%	53	25%	214									
مشاهده صحیح	نرخ مثبت صحیح	مشاهده غلط	نرخ منفی غلط	مشاهدات										
				1498										

The CASME database was the only micro-expression facial texture database used in this study. The results obtained from the proposed method on this database, with 1498 samples or observations, are presented in Table 5 - 10. These results show that, in the testing phase, the method achieved an accuracy of 70.37% with the SVM classifier and 71.76% with the MLNN classifier. The accuracy achieved with the MLNN classifier shows an improvement of 0.57% compared to the 2017 study [112], which is fairly acceptable. Additionally, Table 5 - 11, Table 5 - 12, Table 5 - 13, and Table 5 - 14 display the results of the proposed method for facial expression recognition using the MLNN classifier on the JAFFE, VAP RGB-D, VAP RGB-D-T, and EURECOM databases, respectively. The results include accuracy rates of 97.3%, 98.01%, 97.59%, and 99%, with

improvements of 2.15%, 5.12%, 2.52%, and 11.91% compared to the studies [74], [56], [57], and [78] for the JAFFE, VAP RGB-D, VAP RGB-D-T, and EURECOM databases, respectively. It is noteworthy that in all tables, we observe the classification overlap or error in the classes (happiness-surprise-fear) and (sadness-anger) due to the similarity of their movement units, which constitute the highest classification errors. Additionally, the neutral state also shows a relatively high error and similarity rate with the other six facial expressions and micro-expressions.

Table 5 - 11 The confusion matrix of the training data for facial expression recognition, using the JAFFE database with the MLNN classifier

خنثی	29	99%	1	1%	-	-	-	-	-
خوشحالی	1	1%	30	99%	-	-	-	-	-
عصبانیت	-	-	-	28	96%	2	4%	-	-
غم	-	-	-	1	2%	29	98%	-	-
تعجب	-	-	1	2%	-	-	29	98%	-
انزجار	-	-	-	-	1	1%	-	28	99%
ترس	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	3%	30
-	خنثی	خوشحالی	عصبانیت	غم	تعجب	انزجار	ترس		
	29	99%	1	1%	30				
	30	99%	1	1%	31				
	28	96%	2	4%	30				
	29	98%	1	2%	30				
	29	98%	1	2%	30				
	28	99%	1	1%	29				
	30	97%	2	3%	32				
مشاهده صحیح	نرخ مثبت صحیح	مشاهده غلط	نرخ منفی غلط	مشاهدات					
				212					

Table 5 - 12 The confusion matrix of the training data for facial expression recognition, using the VAP RGB-D database with the MLNN classifier

خنثی	172	99%	2	1%	-	-	-
خوشحالی	4	2%	170	98%	-	-	-
عصبانیت	-	-	-	172	99%	2	1%
غم	-	-	-	-	174	100%	-
تعجب	-	-	-	-	-	174	100%
-	خنثی	خوشحالی	عصبانیت	غم	تعجب		
	172	99%	2	1%	174		
	170	98%	4	2%	174		
	172	99%	2	1%	174		
	174	100%	0	-	174		
	174	100%	0	-	174		
مشاهده صحیح	نرخ مثبت صحیح	مشاهده غلط	نرخ منفی غلط	مشاهدات			
				870			

Table 5 - 13 The confusion matrix of the training data for facial expression recognition, using the VAP RGB-D-T database with the classifier

خنثی	719	94%	30	4%	-	16	2%	719	94%	16	6%	765
خوشحالی	-	-	726	95%	-	38	5%	726	95%	38	5%	765
عصبانیت	-	-	-	-	765	100%	-	765	100%	0	-	765
تعجب	-	-	23	3%	-	742	97%	742	97%	23	3%	765
-	خنثی	خوشحالی	عصبانیت	تعجب	مشاهده صحیح	نرخ مثبت صحیح	مشاهده غلط	نرخ منفی غلط	مشاهدات	3060		

Table 5 - 14 The confusion matrix of the training data for facial expression recognition, using the EURECOM database with the MLNN classifier

خنثی	204	98%	4	2%	-	204	98%	4	2%	208	
خوشحالی	2	1%	204	98%	2	1%	204	98%	4	2%	208
تعجب	-	-	-	-	208	100%	208	100%	0	-	208
-	خنثی	خوشحالی	تعجب	مشاهده صحیح	نرخ مثبت صحیح	مشاهده غلط	نرخ منفی غلط	مشاهدات	624		

Table 5 - 15, Table 5 - 16, Table 5 - 17, and Table 5 - 18 show the results obtained by the proposed method for gender recognition on the KDEF, EURECOM, FEEDB, and IKFDB databases, using the MLNN classifier. Given that gender recognition is a binary classification task (male and female), the proposed method achieved high accuracy on the mentioned databases compared to previous studies. With a recognition accuracy of 97% compared to the study by Mr. Huynh in 2012 [70], which achieved an accuracy of 85.90%, the proposed method shows an improvement of 11.1%. Additionally, the achieved recognition accuracies of 100%, 97.16%, and 91.1% for gender recognition on the KDEF, IKFDB, and FEEDB databases (from left to right) for the first time can be considered significant results.

Table 5 - 15 Confusion matrix of training data for gender recognition, KDEF database with MLNN classifier

مذکر	490	100%	-	490	100%	0	-	490
مؤنث	-	-	490	100%	490	100%	0	490
-	مذکر	مؤنث	مشاهده صحیح	نرخ مثبت صحیح	مشاهده غلط	نرخ منفی غلط	مشاهدات	980

Table 5 - 16 Confusion matrix of training data for gender recognition, EURECOM database with MLNN classifier

مذکر	433	95%	23	5%	433	95%	23	5%	456
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مؤنث	4	2%	164	98%	164	98%	4	2%	168
-	مذكر		مؤنث		مشاهده صحيح	نرخ مثبت صحيح	مشاهده غلط	نرخ منفي غلط	مشاهدات
									624

Table 5 - 17 Confusion matrix of training data for gender recognition, FEEDB database with MLNN classifier

مذكر	440	88%	60	12%	440	88%	60	12%	500
مؤنث	40	8%	460	92%	460	92%	40	8%	500
-	مذكر		مؤنث		مشاهده صحيح	نرخ مثبت صحيح	مشاهده غلط	نرخ منفي غلط	مشاهدات
									1000

Table 5 - 18 Confusion matrix of training data for gender recognition, IKFDB database with MLNN classifier

مذكر	2376	99%	24	1%	2376	99%	24	1%	2400
مؤنث	16	1%	1584	99%	1584	99%	16	1%	1600
-	مذكر		مؤنث		مشاهده صحيح	نرخ مثبت صحيح	مشاهده غلط	نرخ منفي غلط	مشاهدات
									4000

All tables related to the confusion matrix of the training data are for the proposed method, and as previously mentioned, the experimental results are provided in Table 5 - 1 along with the explanations at the end of the tables. Figure 5–2 and Figure 5–3 show the bar plot of the results of the proposed method for facial expression and micro-expression recognition using the IKFDB database. In these charts, the horizontal axis represents the 7 main classes of expressions and micro-expressions, and the vertical axis shows the recognition accuracy.

Figure 5-2 Bar plot of the training data results for the IKFDB database (facial expressions)

Figure 5-3 Bar plot of the training data results for the IKFDB database (micro facial expressions)

Table 5 - 19 compares the results obtained from the proposed method with the results obtained by other researchers in the field of facial expression and micro-expression recognition up to 2017. The explanations for these results are

detailed at the beginning and end of Table 5 - 12, Table 5 - 11, Table 5 - 13, Table 5 - 14, Table 5 - 8, and Table 5 - 10.

Table 5 - 19 Comparison of the results obtained and the results from other researchers up to 2017 (facial expression and micro-expression recognition).

پژوهشگر و سال	پایگاه داده	دقت تشخیص (آزمایشی)	دقت تشخیص روش پیشنهادی (آزمایشی)
Hg RI, Jasek P) 2012(VAP RGB-D	92.88%	98.14%
Wei-LunChao) 2015(JAFFE	94.88%	97.3%
Oliu Simon, Marc) 2016(VAP RGB-D-T	95.70%	97.59%
Ijjina, Earnest Paul) 2014(Eurecom Kinect	87.98%	99.0%
Sen Yuan, Xia Mao) 2017(Face Grabber	83%	94.91%
(2017) Zheng, Hao	CASME	71.19%	71.76%

5-4 Conclusion

Since facial expression recognition has been a significant focus for researchers, improving existing methods and even developing new methods to increase the accuracy of facial expression recognition is crucial. It is known that the appropriate use of image preprocessing methods and the accurate selection of spatial features in an image can significantly impact the final recognition accuracy. Texture and depth feature extraction methods work well for age, facial expression, and micro-expression recognition on various databases, as well as the proposed and newly created database. Thus, by utilizing the methods proposed in the previous chapter and the classifiers SVM and MLNN, we were able to improve the accuracy of several texture-based and texture-depth-based databases compared to the results achieved by other researchers up until 2017 in facial expression and micro-expression recognition (the main topic), as well as gender recognition (a secondary topic).

Chapter 6 Summary, Conclusion and Recommendations

6-1 Summary and Conclusion

Enhancing the ability to recognize facial expressions, faces, humans, and any human-related factors in computer vision is of great importance. As mentioned earlier, the goal of this research is to improve the ability and accuracy of facial expression and micro-expression recognition using texture-depth or RGBD images and videos. This research began by examining the basic concepts of recognition, particularly facial expression recognition. The concepts relevant to image processing, computer vision, machine learning, and statistical pattern recognition were also discussed and explored. The quality and performance of texture and depth data acquisition sensors were analyzed. The background of previous works on facial and micro-expression recognition (the main topic), age estimation, and gender recognition (secondary topics) was reviewed. The structure of texture and depth data was analyzed, and some of the best feature extraction methods from the spatial and frequency domains were examined. New methods for extracting features from texture and depth data were proposed, and some of these spatial features, both in the spatial and frequency domains, were combined to strengthen the recognition power. Additionally, a method for age estimation from database samples was introduced. A new database based on texture and depth data collected by a Kinect sensor was created, overcoming many problems found in similar existing databases. This database is one of the few texture-depth databases that benefit from micro-expression data.

From the results obtained, it is easy to conclude that the proposed methods for any type of texture and depth data, for the purpose of facial expression and micro-expression recognition and gender classification, are highly effective. Combining six spatial features might increase computational load, but it covers all image areas and reduces the error probability to zero. The enhancement of classification accuracy (recognition) in several well-known databases in the field of facial and micro-expression recognition is clearly evident. Moreover, performing facial and micro-expression recognition on databases where these tasks had not been performed previously is another significant contribution of

this research, which has been discussed in detail in the previous chapter. The advantages of this research, or rather its proposed methods, can be summarized as follows:

1. Combining feature extraction methods (spatial and frequency domains) up to 6 methods to overcome changes in the image and increase recognition accuracy, and applying them to various sections extracted from the face for expression and micro-expression recognition.
2. Proposing a new method for face detection in depth images.
3. Introducing a method to extract features from depth images based on the intensity of pixel distance changes with the sensor.
4. Gender recognition from texture-depth images using the proposed methods.
5. Age estimation for database samples based on the pixel density of texture and depth images in the area around the nose.
6. Creating and offering a texture-depth database with Kinect sensor version 2 for high-quality facial and micro-expression recognition to solve the existing problems in current databases in this field.

6-2 Recommendations

Additionally, the following suggestions can be made to improve the proposed methods:

1. Change the proposed face detection method from depth data using evolutionary image segmentation.
2. Use deep learning for selecting the best features (automatically and consciously) to increase recognition accuracy. Algorithms like Auto Encoder and CNN are suitable for this purpose.
3. Convert the proposed age estimation method to a fuzzy estimation approach to present results more clearly.

4. Create a database with more than 7 main facial expressions, using a sensor other than Kinect, so that it can record more than 30 frames per second to aid in the process of micro-expression recognition.
5. Use dimensionality reduction or feature selection methods like Elastic Net, which is a more complete version of Lasso, especially in cases where the number of selected features exceeds the number of samples in the database. This method was not needed in this research.
6. Use feature extraction methods specific to 3D data, such as LBP-Top, LPQ-Top, HAOG, etc.

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